

TECHNISCHE UNIVERSITÄT BERLIN

MASTER THESIS

**Towards a More Refined Training Process
for Neural Networks: Applying
Layer-wise Relevance Propagation to
Understand and Improve Classification
Performance on Imbalanced Datasets**

*Zur Erlangung des akademischen Grades
Master of Science*

in

Fachgebiet Machine Learning
Institut für Softwaretechnik und Theoretische Informatik

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10. Mai 2020

Declaration of Authorship

Hiermit erkläre ich, Leander Weber, an Eides statt, dass ich die vorliegende Arbeit selbstständig und eigenhändig sowie ohne unerlaubte fremde Hilfe und ausschließlich unter Verwendung der aufgeführten Quellen und Hilfsmittel angefertigt habe.

Berlin, den

10.05.2020

Datum

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Unterschrift

Abstract

In this thesis, we consider the problem of neural network (NN) training on imbalanced datasets. The generalization performance of state-of-the-art Deep Neural Networks heavily relies on the dataset composition, and class imbalance can lead to undesirable effects such as overfitting on majority classes or disregard of minority classes. Furthermore, imbalanced datasets are not a rare case, especially when the data is taken from a real-world setting. To mitigate their negative effects on state-of-the-art networks, the training behavior of a neural network on imbalanced data is analyzed and adapted with the goal of achieving a more balanced performance, i.e. with the aim to obtain an improved generalization. For this purpose, heatmaps generated via Layer-wise Relevance Propagation (LRP) (Bach et al., 2015) are employed as a measure of (class-wise) understanding. As an example case, the extremely popular and widely used VGG-16 model (Simonyan and Zisserman, 2014) is chosen as the network architecture and the Adience benchmark (Eidinger, Enbar, and Hassner, 2014) as an imbalanced real-world dataset.

We start with a short overview over the methods relevant for this thesis, i.e., established approaches for dealing with imbalanced datasets when training neural networks and explainability methods, especially LRP.

In a first experiment, the usage of LRP-heatmaps as a measure of understanding is then validated by determining their correlation to traditional evaluation metrics, e.g., test accuracy and F1-score. For this purpose, secondary metrics are derived from the LRP-heatmaps, to enable the comparison to the traditional evaluation metrics. A strong connection between the LRP-heatmap-based metrics and the traditional evaluation metrics is uncovered here. Moreover, we find that the LRP-heatmap-based metrics are indicative of how well the classes separate w.r.t. the prediction function $f(x)$. These properties motivate the second experiment, where the LRP-heatmaps and the secondary metrics derived from them are applied practically for making class-wise adaptations to the NNs' training behavior. Here, the expressivity of LRP-heatmaps is demonstrated for this purpose by achieving more balanced class-wise performances with training-improving methods based on LRP, since, e.g., the derived methods force the neural network model during training to immediately consider previously neglected classes.

Zusammenfassung

In dieser Masterarbeit beschäftigen wir uns mit dem Problem, ein Neuronales Netz (NN) auf unbalancierten Daten zu trainieren. Die Generalisierungsfähigkeit von modernen tiefen Neuronalen Netzen hängt stark von der Zusammensetzung des Datensets ab. Dadurch können ungleich verteilte Daten oft zu unerwünschten Effekten führen, beispielsweise auf quantitativ stärker vertretene Klassen zu overfitten oder Minderheitsklassen zu vernachlässigen. Dazu kommt, dass ungleich verteilte Datensets keine Seltenheit sind, insbesondere wenn die Daten reale Verhältnisse widerspiegeln. Um diese negativen Effekte auf modernen Netzen abzumildern, wird das Verhalten Neuronaler Netze während des Trainings mit unbalancierten Daten untersucht und angepasst, um eine ausgeglichene Leistung zu erreichen. Hierfür werden mittels der Anwendung von "Layer-wise Relevance Propagation" (LRP) (Bach et al., 2015) die erhaltenen Heatmaps als Maß für (klassenspezifisches) Verständnis verwendet. Als Fallbeispiel werden zu diesem Zweck das weit verbreitete und gerne verwendete VGG-16-Modell (Simonyan and Zisserman, 2014) als Netzwerkarchitektur sowie die Adience Benchmark (Eidinger, Enbar, and Hassner, 2014) als ein Datenset ausgewählt, das ungleich verteilt ist und reale Bedingungen widerspiegelt.

Zu Beginn werden die für diese Arbeit relevanten Methoden, d.h. etablierte Vorgehensweisen für den Umgang mit unbalancierten Daten beim Training von Neuronalen Netzen und Methoden zur Erklärbarkeit, insbesondere LRP, kurz und übersichtlich vorgestellt.

In einem ersten Experiment wird dann die Nutzung von LRP-Heatmaps als ein Maß für Verständnis validiert, indem die Korrelation zwischen diesen Heatmaps und klassischeren Evaluationsmethoden, wie Test-Accuracy und F1-Wert untersucht wird. Um den Vergleich mit diesen etablierten Evaluationsmethoden zu ermöglichen, werden hierfür sekundäre Größen aus den LRP-Heatmaps abgeleitet. Dabei wird zum einen ein starker Zusammenhang zwischen den Größen, die auf LRP-Heatmaps basieren, und den klassischen Evaluationsmetriken deutlich. Zum anderen zeigt sich, dass diese Größen eine klassenweise Separierbarkeit bezüglich der Vorhersagefunktion $f(x)$ nahelegen. Diese Eigenschaften veranlassen uns dazu, ein zweites Experiment durchzuführen, bei dem die LRP-Heatmaps und die von ihnen abgeleiteten Größen praktisch angewendet werden, um das Trainingsverhalten eines Neuronalen Netzes klassenweise anzupassen. In diesem Experiment zeigt sich insbesondere die Expressivität der LRP-Heatmaps, da Methoden, die auf ihnen fußen, balanciertere klassenspezifische Leistungen erreichen und beispielsweise ein Neuronales Netz dazu bringen können, vorher vernachlässigte Klassen unmittelbar zu berücksichtigen.

Acknowledgements

Firstly, I would like to thank Prof. Dr. Klaus-Robert Müller for granting me the topic of this thesis. Thereby, he offered the opportunity to write this master thesis in my field of passion, the current and ongoing research area of artificial intelligence and machine learning.

I also want to express my gratitude towards Dr. Wojciech Samek for enabling me to use the resources of the Fraunhofer Heinrich-Hertz-Institute, without which the execution of the experiments in this thesis would not have been possible.

Moreover, I am extremely grateful to Dr. Sebastian Lapuschkin, for his great supervision and mentorship. Through a multitude of discussions, he offered invaluable insights and fresh perspectives into the subject of explainability. With his amicable suggestions and input, he greatly eased the writing of this thesis and was a driving force for its successful completion.

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List of Abbreviations

CAM	Class Activation Mapping
CNN	Convolutional Neural Network
DNN	Deep Neural Network
DTD	Deep Taylor Decomposition
LIME	Local Interpretable Model-agnostic Explanations
LRP	Layer-wise Relevance Propagation
MLP	MultiLayer Perceptron
MSE	Mean Squared Error
NN	Neural Network
ReLU	Rectified Linear Unit
SMOTE	Synthetic Minority Oversampling Technique

Chapter 1

Introduction

In recent years, the field of Machine Learning has gained an increasing amount of popularity. Especially neural networks (NN) and deep learning are being used in a growing variety of applications (Deng, Hinton, and Kingsbury, 2013; Segler, Preuss, and Waller, 2018; Ruseti et al., 2018; Kalash et al., 2018; Muhammad et al., 2018; Levi and Hassner, 2015; Brinker et al., 2018; Arulkumaran, Cully, and Togelius, 2019; Liu et al., 2016), e.g., for image classification (Kalash et al., 2018; Muhammad et al., 2018; Levi and Hassner, 2015; Brinker et al., 2018) where great advances have been made using deep convolutional neural networks (CNNs).

The deep CNNs used in state-of-the-art image classification methods, as all deep neural networks, are data-driven techniques. As such, their performance and convergence behavior heavily rely on the composition of the dataset used for training. Especially a strong imbalance of classes within the dataset can lead to a bad generalization performance, due to the network overfitting on majority classes. However, strongly imbalanced datasets are very common for several applications, e.g., classification of skin cancer (Brinker et al., 2018) or age prediction from face images, as shown in Figure 1.1 for the Adience face recognition dataset (Eidinger, Enbar, and Hassner, 2014). In the latter case, this imbalance stems from the varying representations of different age groups in photos uploaded from smartphone devices. Especially young adults (ages 25–32) are extremely well represented, while other classes, e.g., ages 48–53 are very weakly represented. This data was obtained in an automated manner from Flickr online image albums (Eidinger, Enbar, and Hassner, 2014). Thus, the distribution of the Adience dataset reflects real-world conditions¹ and shows that data imbalance is a very real problem that needs to be addressed in machine learning applications.

When dealing with imbalanced data, samples from majority classes are often discarded (Drummond and Holte, 2003; Liu, Wu, and Zhou, 2009; Rothe, Timofte, and Gool, 2015), or samples for minority classes artificially created (Li et al., 2013; Chawla et al., 2002). However, the former method may throw away useful information, while the latter can distort the existing information. Thus, we aim to change the training behavior of the network on imbalanced data in such a way that the resulting class-wise performance of the network is equalized. For this purpose, we require information where the model is unsure or lacking. While this could be read from the class-wise accuracy or loss to some degree, we aim to utilize *a richer source of information*, reflecting the model’s understanding. Thus, we need to understand the network’s decision making w.r.t. the data, i.e., which parts of an input support or oppose a given class. To explain neural network decisions, various methods exist (Baehrens et al., 2010; Simonyan, Vedaldi, and Zisserman, 2013; Zeiler and Fergus,

¹Here, e.g., direct and indirect exposure to smart phone devices and social media

FIGURE 1.1: Age class distribution in the Adience benchmark dataset. The classes are extremely imbalanced, with the largest class (ages 25–32) containing more than five times the amount of samples of the smallest class (ages 48–53).

2014; Springenberg et al., 2015; Dosovitskiy and Brox, 2016; Kindermans et al., 2018; Bach et al., 2015; Montavon et al., 2017). However, these approaches vary in the type of explanations they provide, and not all of them are feasible for the purposes of this thesis. In particular, Layer-wise Relevance Propagation (LRP) (Bach et al., 2015) is class specific (Kohlbrenner et al., 2019) without resorting to contrastive approaches. The relevances computed by LRP have a meaningful sign and, if the best practice is followed, LRP is sensitive to the actual parameter values of a network, in contrast to other explainability methods (Sixt, Granz, and Landgraf, 2019). Thus, it provides the detailed explanations and in-depth understanding of neural network decisions that we require, which can be visualized in the form of interpretable heatmaps. As these heatmaps offer insights into the neural network’s decision-making, we aim to utilize them to refine the training process on imbalanced datasets, thereby achieving a more balanced classification performance.

1.1 Goals and Own Contributions

Firstly, we aim to understand the training behavior and performance of neural networks (NNs) on imbalanced data. Towards this goal, we employ the Layer-wise Relevance Propagation (LRP) method to obtain explanations of the NN’s decision-making in the form of LRP-heatmaps. Secondly, we plan on applying the insights we gained there practically, and utilize them to achieve a more balanced classification performance of a NN on imbalanced data.

For these purposes, we make the following key contributions:

1. We explore and validate a connection between the relevance maps obtained via LRP and more traditional metrics that measure network classification performance, e.g., test accuracy and F1-score.

- (a) We propose secondary metrics based on LRP-heatmaps in order to quantify them and obtain a measure of the understanding that a network has of the data without requiring label information.
 - (b) We validate these proposed LRP-heatmap-based metrics by comparing them with traditional performance metrics and interpret their behavior over the course of training.
2. We apply LRP-heatmaps and the proposed metrics derived from them in order to balance the performance on imbalanced data. For this purpose, we employ the following two approaches:
 - (a) We resample the data that is fed to the network.
 - (b) We scale the class-wise losses.

1.2 Structure of the Thesis

After the short introduction to the topic (Chapter 1) and the summary of our goals and own contributions for this thesis (Section 1.1), the following Chapter 2 will offer an overview over the fundamental basics of deep learning, especially convolutional neural networks (CNN) which are applied in our experiments. Since we aim to equalize NN classification performance on imbalanced data via Layer-wise Relevance Propagation (LRP) in this thesis, Chapter 2 will furthermore provide an overview about existing approaches to the two underlying problems of handling imbalanced datasets in machine learning applications and explaining the decision-making of NNs.

In Chapter 3, we will then go into further detail about LRP, as this is the explanation method we choose to employ. The reasoning for this decision is illustrated in Section 2.3.3.

The following Chapter 4 will then outline the general setup of our experiments, i.e., expound our choice of neural network architecture, dataset, and evaluation metrics. The specific setup of each experiment is provided in further detail within the respective Chapters, i.e., 5 and 6. Here, the series of experiments in Chapter 5 aims to validate whether the heatmaps provided by the LRP-method do in fact offer a valid estimation a NNs generalization performance. This is done by deriving secondary metrics from these heatmaps which are then compared with traditional performance measures. The results of these experiments are then detailed and discussed in-depth.

Building on that, the three experimental series in Chapter 6 then focus on applying the knowledge obtained in Chapter 5 in practice. This is either done by using the proposed LRP-heatmap-based metrics to parameterize established methods for handling imbalanced datasets introduced in Chapter 2, i.e., batch resampling and scaling class-wise losses. Again, the results of these experiments are presented and discussed.

Lastly, Chapter 7 will summarize the core results obtained in this thesis, offer concluding statements, and provide an outlook over possible future research directions.

Some additional figures and results can be found in the Appendix.

Chapter 2

Background

This section will provide an overview of existing approaches to tasks related to this thesis, i.e., deep learning, handling imbalanced data, and explaining the decisions of a deep neural network (DNN).

2.1 Basics of Deep Neural Networks

FIGURE 2.1: Schematic of a simple Multilayer Perceptron (MLP). It is structured into multiple layers of neurons, including hidden layers (here one for simplicity), an input layer, and an output layer. Each neuron takes a number of (weighted) inputs and a bias, aggregates them, and applies some potentially nonlinear transfer function to compute an output. This output is either weighted and used as the input of a neuron of the following layer or, in the output layer, denotes one of the network's outputs or predictions. This interleaving structure of neurons thus makes up the neural network.

With a design that is (roughly) inspired by biological neural networks, artificial neural networks (NNs) consist of a multitude of relatively simple, interconnected elements, the *neurons*. In the most basic type of NN, the Multilayer Perceptron (MLP), the neurons are structured into layers, with the neurons of each layer l usually only receiving input from the previous layer $l - 1$ (see Figure 2.1). Here, these layers are divided into an input layer, hidden layers, and an output layer. Each neuron j , $j \in [1, m]$ at layer l receives a number of inputs $x_i^{(l-1)}$, $i \in [1, n]$ that are scaled by

the weights ($w_{ij}^{(l-1,l)}$). These scaled inputs are first summed at neuron j , often with a bias term $b_j^{(l)}$ added that represents a predisposition of neuron j :

$$h_j^{(l)} = \sum_{i=1}^n w_{ij}^{(l-1,l)} x_i^{(l-1)} + b_j^{(l)} \quad (2.1)$$

To compute the neuron's output $x_j^{(l)}$, the aggregation $h_j^{(l)}$ is used as the input to an activation function $g_j^{(l)}$, i.e.,

$$x_j^{(l)} = g_j^{(l)}(h_j^{(l)}) \quad (2.2)$$

For non-constant, bounded, monotonously increasing, and continuous functions $g_j^{(l)}$, i.e., a subset of nonlinear functions, even MLPs with only one hidden layer are able to approximate any function in theory, as proven by (Funahashi, 1989). While the above properties for activation functions are not always strictly adhered to, common choices with various desirable properties include, among others: The sigmoid, hyperbolic tangent, and rectified linear unit (ReLU) functions (Figure 2.2). The resulting output $x_j^{(l)}$ of neuron j can then, in turn, be used as the input for neurons of layer $l + 1$. Multiple neurons connected in this manner thus form a NN.

FIGURE 2.2: Overview of some popular choices of nonlinear activation functions. (Left to right) the sigmoid ($\frac{1}{1+e^{-x}}$), hyperbolic tangent ($\tanh(x)$), and rectified linear unit (ReLU) ($\max(0, x)$) functions. Here parametrized for a variation of parameters p .

A NN can theoretically approximate any function. As such, similar to other machine learning methods, it can be fitted on some data w.r.t. a very specific task, learning underlying regularities within the data in order to be able to predict certain quantities, e.g., to classify images or text data into categories, or predict the continuation of sequences. This learning process is called training and is done by adapting the parameters, i.e., weights and biases within the network to achieve a higher prediction score. For this purpose, the true assignments to each datapoint used for training need to be known beforehand, so that the network's current performance can be quantified and its error evaluated, in order to minimize this error towards a local optimum, e.g., via Stochastic Gradient Descent (LeCun et al., 2012). As such, NNs are data-driven methods, since their parameters are adapted to solve a certain task w.r.t. given data, and can be seen as algorithms that partially program themselves. However, with this property, also new issues arise, e.g., as a NN's training depends on the data it has seen, any (hidden) biases or errors within the data will also be reflected in the network's predictions.

While (Funahashi, 1989) has proven that a MLP with one hidden layer with a sufficient number of neurons activated by a certain subset of nonlinear functions can theoretically approximate any function, in practice, DNNs with a multitude of layers seem to achieve far better performances (Brahma, Wu, and She, 2016; Lin and Tegmark, 2016). DNNs are by far more difficult to train than shallow networks, as they require more data due to their larger number of parameters and converge slower, however, they also seem to be able to represent features hierarchically and with increasing complexity, explaining their superior ability to generalize (Zeiler and Fergus, 2014).

In this thesis, the networks' task always consists of predicting the class of an image from a set of possible labels, i.e., image classification, where the pixels of an image are used as the input to the network, and a score for each class is its output. For this scenario, a specialized type of NN, the convolutional neural network (CNN) (LeCun et al., 1998), has been found to perform extremely well. CNNs make use of convolutional layers consisting of multiple filters that each learn to determine the existence of one specific feature at a certain position in the layer's input. A consecutive pooling layer then allows for invariance against that specific position of a feature within the input, e.g., by only propagating the maximally activated filter within a small group of filters forward. Thus, the first convolution-pooling-combination could, e.g., determine the existence for a horizontal edge anywhere within an input image, and, building on this in a hierarchical manner, the second one could then determine the existence of a certain pattern of edges and so on until deeper layers are able to determine very high-level features, e.g., the existence of an eye in a face image. In fact, CNNs are able to vastly outperform other methods on the datasets relevant to this thesis (Levi and Hassner, 2015), e.g., the Adience dataset. Thus, as they are the state-of-the-art machine learning method for this type of task, we use CNNs for the purposes of this thesis.

2.2 Handling Imbalanced Datasets

Training a DNN on imbalanced data is a difficult process, as the number of provided samples varies strongly between classes and the network thus becomes extremely prone to overfitting. For alleviating this issue, various approaches exist. In this thesis, we categorize these into *data-focused* and *algorithm-focused* methods.

Since the root of the imbalance problem lies with the inequally distributed dataset, data-focused approaches seek to rebalance the data. The simplest way to achieve this goal is *undersampling*, where samples from strongly represented classes are randomly discarded to equalize the sample frequency per class. While this strategy reduces the imbalance problem efficiently (Drummond and Holte, 2003), it throws away a large amount of potential information (Liu, Wu, and Zhou, 2009). In contrast, *oversampling* (Li et al., 2013) increases the number of samples in the minority classes, e.g., by randomly duplicating or augmenting datapoints. This method, however, may lead to overfitting (Wang et al., 2016) on those minority classes. A more sophisticated *oversampling* strategy is reflected in the *Synthetic Minority Oversampling Technique* (SMOTE) algorithm (Chawla et al., 2002), where new, artificial datapoints are created using interpolation between samples of minority classes. However, SMOTE still suffers from problems like over-generalization and variance (He and Garcia, 2009), making it difficult to apply to very complex data or data with a high variation such as images.

In contrast to data-focused strategies, the second category of approaches for learning on imbalanced data, algorithm-focused methods, does not try to balance the data. Instead, they approach the problem from an algorithmic perspective (Wang et al., 2016) by making the classifier more sensitive towards minority classes (Khan et al., 2018). In the context of NNs, this is usually done by adapting the loss function in favor of these minority classes. For this purpose, cost-sensitive approaches (Kukar and Kononenko, 1998; Chung, Lin, and Yang, 2016) can be employed, where class-wise costs for misclassifying samples are considered. However, describing these costs explicitly may often prove challenging or even impossible (Wang et al., 2016). Other approaches incorporate the class frequency directly into the loss function, as to prevent a large number of small losses of frequent classes from overwhelming large losses of infrequent classes (Lin et al., 2020).

Data-focused approaches aim to remedy the inherent imbalance within the dataset, while algorithm-focused approaches employ the class-wise sample frequencies or hyperparameters, e.g., class-wise misclassification costs, in order to tell the classifier to "pay more attention" to certain classes. However, both strategies do not consider the classifiers learning behavior. Especially in the context of DNNs, the successful learning of a good class representation may depend on a multitude of factors, and dataset imbalance in itself may not be a hindrance. For instance, a small number of samples may be sufficient for some classes, while other classes may prove more difficult to learn, requiring more samples. To develop such a strategy that incorporates and requires a deeper understanding of the networks' behavior, we first need to find a suitable method for comprehending its decision-making.

2.3 Understanding Neural Network Decisions

In recent years, NNs have been growing increasingly popular for a variety of applications. They are highly complex models which consist of an enormous number of non-linear, interacting parts (Yosinski et al., 2015) that learn "end-to-end", i.e., are fed some data which they then learn to distinguish and understand. While the features learned by NNs are potentially better than any hand-crafted ones, especially for complex problems, they in turn offer little control about the model and their decision-making cannot always be easily interpreted. Thus, NNs are often viewed as black-boxes. To gain a better understanding of their decisions, various approaches have been proposed.

2.3.1 Explanation Vectors, Saliency Maps, and Meaningful Perturbation

The first family of methods mainly employs *Sensitivity Analysis* to understand how changing a single input of a nonlinear classifier (e.g., a NN) affects its output. For Bayesian classification, (Baehrens et al., 2010) compute *Explanation Vectors* for individual samples as the partial derivatives of the probability function of a learned model at each sample. Thus, they are able to explain the classifier's class choice for each individual datapoint by determining the direction in which a datapoint can be modified in order to change its predicted label.

In the context of Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs) for image classification, (Simonyan, Vedaldi, and Zisserman, 2013) propose *Saliency Maps* as a method for visualizing the network's class representations. For a given sample image I_0 , the authors approximate the network's class score function around I_0 via first-order Taylor expansion. Pixel-wise explanations are obtained similarly to (Baehrens et al., 2010), by computing the partial derivative of the approximated class score function

w.r.t. the image. Thus, (Simonyan, Vedaldi, and Zisserman, 2013) are able to determine how sensitive the network’s prediction is towards modifications to single pixels.

(Fong and Vedaldi, 2017) introduce the *Meaningful Perturbation* method. With the goal of finding a maximally informative deletion mask for each sample, i.e., a minimal deletion mask that, when applied to the sample, reduces the model’s classification confidence w.r.t. a specific class as much as possible. For this purpose, they employ a meta-predictor to learn that sample-specific mask using gradient descent. Due to their usage of the model’s gradient, the approach of (Fong and Vedaldi, 2017) is similar to (Simonyan, Vedaldi, and Zisserman, 2013), though they improve upon (Simonyan, Vedaldi, and Zisserman, 2013) with their consecutive application of the gradient during the meta-predictor’s learning process. However, this also increases the computational cost considerably, as a meta-predictor needs to be fit to each explained sample separately. More concisely, the Meaningful Perturbation method costs $\mathcal{O}(n)$ in terms of standard NN backward passes, with $n = 300$ being suggested by the authors. In contrast, the approaches presented by (Baehrens et al., 2010) and (Simonyan, Vedaldi, and Zisserman, 2013) only cost $\mathcal{O}(1)$.

By their use of partial gradients w.r.t. specific samples (Baehrens et al., 2010; Simonyan, Vedaldi, and Zisserman, 2013) or the learning of a deletion mask (Fong and Vedaldi, 2017), the methods mentioned above focus on determining which (minimal) *changes* would have to be made to a sample in order to alter its predicted class. However, for the purposes of this thesis, we require information on which parts of the sample, i.e., which image pixels, speak most strongly for or against a certain class, since we aim to utilize this information for developing a training strategy that incorporates understanding about why a network decides for or against a certain class.

2.3.2 DeConvNet, Guided Backpropagation, and LIME

The second family of methods focuses on interpreting concepts that single neurons or neuron layers have learned (Zeiler and Fergus, 2014; Springenberg et al., 2015; Dosovitskiy and Brox, 2016; Kindermans et al., 2018). For specific CNNs, (Zeiler and Fergus, 2014) introduce the *DeConvNet* that inverts the convolutional layers via unpooling, rectification, and transposed filtering. Thus, they are able to map specific activations back to the input space (Zeiler and Fergus, 2014), thereby visualizing a pattern which corresponds to the components of a given input that caused the activation, i.e., the *signal* (Kindermans et al., 2018).

The technique of (Zeiler and Fergus, 2014) is designed for a very specific CNN. Building on this approach and combining it with the method of (Simonyan, Vedaldi, and Zisserman, 2013), (Springenberg et al., 2015) propose *Guided Backpropagation* which — in contrast to *DeConvNet* — does not rely on the presence of max-pooling layers in the CNN and produces a sharper visualization of features for higher layers.

The above methods visualize the discriminative features of the input data, as seen by the trained network. However, to be applicable, they require modifications to the backward pass. They furthermore impose strong assumptions on the network architecture. In contrast, the *Local Interpretable Model-agnostic Explanations* (LIME) approach presented by (Ribeiro, Singh, and Guestrin, 2016) does not make any assumptions about the model and does not require any modifications of the backward pass. For this approach, for each sample $x \in \mathbb{R}^d$ the authors introduce a binary vector notation $x' \in \{0, 1\}^{d'}$ declaring the presence of d' interpretable components (e.g., super-pixels for image classification). Their goal is then to fit an explanation model

g of small complexity that can predict a class using x' as input and that maximizes the local fidelity of the explanation, i.e., for samples z that are in close proximity to x , the explanation model prediction $g(z')$, with $z' \in \{0, 1\}^{d'}$ analogously to x' , should be close to the original model's prediction $f(z)$. Interpretability of the explanation is furthermore ensured by limiting the number of interpretable components.

While LIME is model-independent and ensures interpretability and local faithfulness of explanations, it has a high computational cost, i.e., $\mathcal{O}(n)$ in terms of standard NN backward passes, as each single explanation requires sampling n instances z around x , obtaining a prediction on each of them and fitting g . In practice, (Ribeiro, Singh, and Guestrin, 2016) sample $n = 5000$ instances, leading to explanation times that strongly depend on type of model f used. E.g., *per explanation*, this procedure takes under 3 seconds for random forests and around 10 minutes for certain DNNs. In contrast, the methods proposed by (Zeiler and Fergus, 2014) and (Springenberg et al., 2015) only cost $\mathcal{O}(1)$. LIME is further dependent on the choice of the explanation model type and the number d' of allowed interpretable components, which may limit the power of its explanations. Furthermore, like (Zeiler and Fergus, 2014) and (Springenberg et al., 2015), the authors of (Ribeiro, Singh, and Guestrin, 2016) only find the features that are important for a decision, but do not quantify the importance of each feature, i.e., explain how each feature influences a specific decision or how features are combined to decide for or against a certain class.

2.3.3 Prediction Difference, CAM, and Layer-wise Relevance Propagation

Similarly to the methods described in Section 2.3.2, the techniques in the following section visualize discriminative features in the input data, however, they also incorporate how strongly each feature contributes towards a specific output. In the context of image classification, (Zintgraf et al., 2017) propose the *Prediction Difference* method. Here, a *relevance score* is computed for each pixel of an input image. This relevance score essentially denotes how much and in which way each pixel contributes to the prediction output of a classifier. Positive and negative relevances can be distinguished as supporting or opposing the decision, respectively. To determine the pixel-wise relevances for a given input image and target class, (Zintgraf et al., 2017) first select $k \times k$ -sized pixel patches in a sliding window fashion. Around each of these, larger patches are sampled s times and the probability of the target class predicted with each larger patch removed from the input. The relevance of each pixel is then obtained by averaging the probability for all removed patches that contained the pixel and comparing it with the predicted probability for the original image input. The resulting relevances can then be easily visualized as a heatmap.

While the technique of (Zintgraf et al., 2017) offers a thorough explanation of how different features of the input affect NN decisions, it is computationally very expensive. More concisely, it costs $\mathcal{O}(s \cdot n)$ in terms of standard NN backward passes, with n denoting the number of pixels per image, as it requires a multitude of NN predictions to obtain a single heatmap and is thus not viable for the purposes of this thesis.

As a computationally more efficient method, (Zhou et al., 2016) introduce the *Class Activation Mapping* (CAM). For a restricted network structure of a CNN that ends with the sequence of a convolutional layer, a global average pooling layer, and a softmax layer, the authors are able to construct discriminative heatmaps showing class-specific regions in an input image. These *Class Activation Maps* are constructed by backpropagating the softmax activations back to the last convolutional layer and upsampling the result to the size of the original input image. This method

is improved upon by (Selvaraju et al., 2017; Selvaraju et al., 2020), who introduce *Grad-CAM* as a generalized version of CAM applicable to various NN architectures and intermediate layers. Grad-CAM and CAM are computationally efficient, as they cost $\mathcal{O}(1)$ in terms of standard NN backward passes, however, even Grad-CAM is still only applicable to rectified convolutional layers within a NN architecture, thus limiting its applicability when explanations for arbitrary layers of a network of arbitrary architecture (i.e., with non-linearities other than rectified linear units (ReLU)) are desired.

(Bach et al., 2015) introduce *Layer-wise Relevance Propagation* (LRP) which, similar to (Zintgraf et al., 2017), assigns a *relevance score* to each pixel of an input image. However, here the relevance score is obtained in a computationally efficient way by decomposing the classification output consecutively into sums of feature relevances, until the input-level is reached and pixel-wise relevances are obtained. E.g., in the context of NNs, this decomposition is performed layer-wise backwards from output to input, costing $\mathcal{O}(1)$ in terms of standard NN backward passes. Finally, the computed pixel-wise relevance scores are visualized as a heatmap. While (Bach et al., 2015) propose LRP for image classification, it is also applicable to other contexts, e.g., natural language processing (Arras et al., 2017) or recommendation systems (Bharadhwaj, 2018). As we employ the LRP method from (Bach et al., 2015) extensively in this thesis, it will be described in further detail in Chapter 3.

(Montavon et al., 2017) provide a theoretically founded perspective on LRP from a viewpoint of (deep) Taylor Decomposition by approximating the relevances via first-order Taylor Decomposition, resulting in the *Deep Taylor Decomposition* method (DTD). However, DTD in turn makes additional assumptions about the model, i.e., that all biases be zero or smaller. For the pretrained models we aim to use in this thesis (see Chapter 4), however, this property may not always be ensured. (Kinderdams et al., 2018) further extend LRP and DTD with the *PatternAttribution* by distinguishing between a signal part and a distractor part of the input. An estimator for the signal is employed to consider only the contribution of the estimated signal to the prediction, thereby aiming to ignore the distractor which results in clearer heatmaps. However, the patterns that separate signal and distractor are learned for each model. In this thesis we aim to compute explanations repeatedly at various points during the training of a NN. As the model is different at each training step, utilizing PatternAttribution would thus be extremely costly for our purposes.

LRP is able to explain which parts of an input support or oppose a certain output and can even offer information about by which degree the various input features influence a decision. The LRP-based techniques can further be applied to any layer in a NN, yielding explanations about all computational stages in a network. Thus, these methods are able to explain NN decisions very thoroughly and efficiently, making them the best choice for the purposes of this thesis. More precisely, LRP does not impose as many constraints as DTD and is in our experimental setting less computationally costly than PatternAttribution. Additionally, there exist available implementations for LRP (Alber et al., 2019) that are closely integrated in state of the art deep learning frameworks, i.e., Tensorflow (Abadi et al., 2016) and Keras (Chollet et al., 2015). Due to these properties, we use LRP for our experiments as the basis for understanding NN performance on imbalanced data and aim to equalize this performance by using various metrics derived from the obtained LRP-heatmaps.

Chapter 3

Layer-wise Relevance Propagation — An Overview

To visualize and quantify the decision making of a Neural Network (NN), we utilize the heatmaps generated by Layer-wise Relevance Propagation (LRP). This method was introduced by (Bach et al., 2015), and is further explored in subsequent publications, such as the recent (Lapuschkin, 2019) and (Montavon et al., 2019). It offers in-depth explanations, as already established in Section 2.3.3. The following explanations are based on (Bach et al., 2015) and (Lapuschkin, 2019), where LRP is defined for a general classifier as a set of constraints: The model f should be decomposable into different layers of computation, with the first being the input layer and the last being the classifier's real-valued output. Then, the intermediate representation of data at layer l can be modeled as a vector, i.e.,

$$z = (z_i^{(l)}) \in \mathbb{R}^{\dim(l)} \quad (3.1)$$

Under the assumption that each relevance score $R_j^{(l+1)}$ for each component $z_j^{(l+1)}$ at the following layer $l + 1$ is already known, LRP then aims to compute the relevance score $R_i^{(l)}$ for each component $z_i^{(l)}$, while conserving the relevance sum globally over all layers, i.e.,

$$\forall l : \sum_i R_i^{(l)} = \sum_j R_j^{(l+1)} \quad (3.2)$$

However, as a decomposition that only satisfies Equation (3.2) is not necessarily meaningful or unique, it is furthermore assumed that f computes mappings z_{ij} between intermediate input data representations from input units i to output units j , with i and j being in consecutive layers. The component z_j at unit j is then obtained via aggregating z_{ij} , e.g., as

$$z_j = \sum_i z_{ij}, \text{ s.t. } i \text{ is mapped to } j \quad (3.3)$$

Corresponding to the (forward) mappings z_{ij} , the relevance $R_i^{(l)}$ is expressed in terms of (backward) relevance messages $R_{i \leftarrow j}^{(l+1)}$, with

$$\sum_i R_{i \leftarrow j}^{(l+1)} = R_j^{(l+1)}, \text{ s.t. } i \text{ contributes to } j \quad (3.4)$$

i.e., the relevance being conserved locally. The specific relevance propagation rule satisfying Equation (3.4) depends on the specific computational graph and the role of the components within it, however, it can be expressed in a general fashion as

$$R_{i \leftarrow j}^{(l,l+1)} = \frac{z_{ij}}{z_j} \cdot R_j^{(l+1)} \quad (3.5)$$

with $\frac{z_{ij}}{z_j}$ measuring to what extent z_{ij} contributes to z_j . Here, a positive contribution of z_{ij} to z_j , that is, both having the same sign, results in a positively signed proportion of the given relevance quality $R_j^{(l+1)}$, while different signs lead to a negative one. Often, the components use a bias, which here is modelled as a regular neuron, for computing their output, as it is the case for various common model types, e.g., NNs. In this instance, part of the relevance "leaks" to the bias, as is desired since the bias contributes to the model's output. However, while relevance is still conserved locally (Equation (3.4)), Equation (3.2) does not hold anymore in general. This issue can be solved by adding dedicated bias nodes to the model or by relaxing the layer-wise relevance conservation property (for details cf. (Lapuschkin, 2019) Section 2.2.4).

$R_i^{(l)}$ is then obtained by aggregating the incoming relevance messages:

$$R_i^{(l)} = \sum_j R_{i \leftarrow j}^{(l,l+1)} = \sum_j \frac{z_{ij}}{z_j} \cdot R_j^{(l+1)} \quad (3.6)$$

Equation (3.6) applies to all components except for those of the last layer, the relevances of which are initialized with the corresponding model outputs. Equation (3.6) can be iteratively applied from output to input, yielding the relevances of all layers of the model.

Due to Equation (3.5) being unbounded for small z_j , and to achieve specific goals, four advanced decomposition rules are proposed:

The **ϵ -Rule** stabilizes this unboundedness by replacing Equation (3.5) with

$$R_{i \leftarrow j}^{(l,l+1)} = \frac{z_{ij}}{z_j + \epsilon \cdot \text{sign}(z_j)} \cdot R_j^{(l+1)} \quad (3.7)$$

with $\epsilon \geq 0$ and $\text{sign}(0) = 1$. However, in a similar manner as for the bias, relevance will leak to ϵ , with larger ϵ absorbing more relevance.

In contrast, the **$\alpha\beta$ -Rule** does not absorb any additional relevance. Here, positive and negative contributions to the relevance message are viewed separately, i.e.,

$$R_{i \leftarrow j}^{(l,l+1)} = \left(\alpha \frac{z_{ij}^+}{z_j^+} + \beta \frac{z_{ij}^-}{z_j^-} \right) \cdot R_j^{(l+1)} \quad (3.8)$$

so that $\alpha + \beta = 1$ and $\alpha \geq 0$. With z_{ij}^+ and z_{ij}^- respectively denoting the positive and negative parts of the contributions z_{ij} — i.e. $z_{ij}^+ = \max(0, z_{ij})$ and $z_{ij}^- = \min(0, z_{ij})$ —, α and β allow for a manual control over their influence on the relevance computation. This property can be desirable for some model architectures, e.g., for NNs with ReLU activations. The parameter choices suggested by (Lapuschkin, 2019) are $\alpha = 1, \beta = 0$ and $\alpha = 2, \beta = -1$, with the former only considering the activating mappings z_{ij}^+ , while the latter also incorporates the inhibitory signals z_{ij}^- . However, if there are either no z_{ij}^+ or no z_{ij}^- for a given j , the relevance conservation property (Equation (3.2)) does not hold anymore. Instead, the relevance contribution $R_{i \leftarrow j}^{(l,l+1)}$ is scaled by the factor β or α , respectively. With a slight adaption to Equation (3.8), however, this issue is easily avoidable:

$$R_{i \leftarrow j}^{(l,l+1)} = \frac{1}{\gamma} \left(\alpha \frac{z_{ij}^+}{z_j^+} + \beta \frac{z_{ij}^-}{z_j^-} \right) \cdot R_j^{(l+1)}$$

$$\gamma = \begin{cases} \alpha & \text{if } z_j^- = 0 \\ \beta & \text{if } z_j^+ = 0 \\ 1 & \text{else} \end{cases} \quad (3.9)$$

For the purpose of projecting the relevance values of intermediate layers onto the input, i.e., in order to stop the backwards relevance propagation at a certain layer, but map the relevances of this layer to the input space, the **b-Rule** is first introduced by (Bach et al., 2016) as

$$R_{i \leftarrow j}^{(l,l+1)} = \frac{1}{\sum_{i'} 1} \cdot R_j^{(l+1)} \quad (3.10)$$

distributing the relevance at unit j equally onto input units i . i' iterates over the units in layer l , as does i . Alternatively, the **w^2 -Rule**

$$R_{i \leftarrow j}^{(l,l+1)} = \frac{w_{ij}^2}{\sum_{i'} w_{i'j}^2} \cdot R_j^{(l+1)} \quad (3.11)$$

achieves a similar effect to the **b-rule**, but utilizes the learned parameters w of the model.

Up to this point, LRP was described for general (albeit constrained) model and input types. In this thesis, however, we apply LRP to image classification with convolutional neural networks (CNN). This is easily done by adapting Equations (3.5) and (3.6) to this type of architecture. In the NN case, the components z_i of LRP correspond to the network's neurons x_i at layer l , with the output of neurons x_j at the following layer $l + 1$ often being computed via linear projection as

$$z_{ij} = x_i \cdot w_{ij}$$

$$x_j = \sum_i z_{ij} + b_j \quad (3.12)$$

where w_{ij} denotes the (learned) weight between x_i and x_j . b_j is the bias term of neuron x_j . Alternatively, x_j is often computed component-wise via a non-linear activation function σ , i.e.,

$$z_{ij} = \delta_{ij} \cdot \sigma(x_i)$$

$$x_j = \sum_i z_{ij} \quad (3.13)$$

where δ_{ij} specifies the Kronecker-Delta. Equations (3.5) and (3.6) can then be obtained by substituting z_{ij} and $z_j = x_j$ accordingly.

After obtaining the explanation for the decisions of a NN via LRP in the form of *LRP-heatmaps*, we then aim to exploit this information in the following chapters to improve the generalization accuracy of a NN on imbalanced data by adapting its training process in different ways.

Chapter 4

Experimental Setup

As previously stated in Chapter 1, we aim to refine the training process of a neural network (NN) to improve its performance on imbalanced data by exploiting the information provided by LRP-heatmaps. For this purpose, we firstly explore the relationship between LRP-heatmaps and network performance experimentally in Chapter 5. We then propose three different methods for improving the NN training process and perform various experiments to compare and evaluate them in Sections 6.1, 6.2. The setup, conditions, and the evaluation methods for these series of experiments will be explained in this chapter.

4.1 Dataset and Model

As the dataset to train our network on, we employ the Adience benchmark (Eidinger, Enbar, and Hassner, 2014) in the following experiments, which is suitable because it offers a class distribution based on real demographics (w.r.t. direct and indirect social media affinity), as it was obtained from user fotos uploaded automatically from smartphone devices and it provides a collection of face images with corresponding age and gender labels. In this dataset, there are eight age classes (ages 0–2, 4–6, 8–13, 15–20, 25–32, 38–43, 48–53, 60+) and two gender classes (male, female). The gender classes offer a relatively balanced classification setting with 8192 male samples and 9411 female samples, while the age classes offer a strongly imbalanced training setting, as is shown in Figure 1.1. There is furthermore a hidden "person type" imbalance, since some individuals tend to actively take pictures of themselves and in large quantities, while others are only represented passively. However, we do not touch upon this hidden imbalance in this thesis. Thus, in the following experiments, the task the networks are trained on consists of either age or gender classification, with the former being our main focus, since it offers the imbalanced class training setting we aim to examine and improve in this thesis.

As proposed by (Lapuschkin et al., 2017), we mix both available versions of the Adience benchmark dataset for the training set: One version that is cropped and rotated to roughly horizontal face alignment, and another version that is additionally aligned in-plane via the method described by (Eidinger, Enbar, and Hassner, 2014). For the test set we only use the rotation-aligned version. These images are cropped to a square shape and then rescaled to 256×256 pixels. Furthermore we use the cropping methods suggested by (Levi and Hassner, 2015): Before feeding each training sample to the network, a random 224×224 pixel crop (matching the VGG-16 network's input dimensionality) is cut out from the sample and flipped horizontally with a random probability of 50%. For testing model performance, five 224×224 crops are generated for each sample, i.e., four corner crops and one center crop.

Each of these five sub-images is additionally mirrored horizontally, resulting in ten variations for each original test sample, a strategy that led to an increased model performance during test time for both (Levi and Hassner, 2015) and (Lapuschkin et al., 2017), and has thus been established as the standard evaluation scheme for the Adience dataset. Depending on the evaluation method (see Section 4.2), these variations are either treated as independent samples or as different versions of the same sample. Furthermore, to stabilize the training process we scale the pixel intensities of each sample image into the interval $[0, 255]$ and subtract the mean per-pixel color of the Adience dataset.

As a network model, we use the VGG-16 architecture (Simonyan and Zisserman, 2014) since it has performed very well on the Adience benchmark dataset in the past (Lapuschkin et al., 2017; Rothe, Timofte, and Gool, 2018). A summary of the general network model that we use can be found in the Appendix (Table A.1). Within this network, groups of convolutional layers with small kernel sizes (2 to 3) alternate with pooling operations, yielding a very deep model. This structure is followed by two large dense layers, each consisting of 4096 hidden units. For regularization purposes, a dropout probability of 50% is applied after each of these dense layers. To converge to a better local optimum, if not stated otherwise, we do not initialize the networks' starting weights randomly, but instead employ transfer learning, i.e., utilize weights that were pretrained by (Simonyan and Zisserman, 2014) on the ImageNet dataset (Deng et al., 2009) as starting weights. We choose these weights because they contain prior knowledge about image classification that is, however, not specific to the Adience dataset. As such, the model does not have to learn the basic structures necessary for classifying images, but still needs to understand the task-specific features. We use a stochastic gradient descent (LeCun et al., 2012) optimizer with a learning rate of 0.0001, except for the experiment described in Chapter 5, and a momentum of 0.9.

The training of this network is done in a batch-wise setup, as shown schematically in Figure 4.1: We partition the training data into larger *data-batches*, and the network is trained on an entire data-batch before moving on to the next one. During this process, each data-batch is in turn split into small *mini-batches* in a common manner, to apply mini-batch gradient descent. In the following, the training process on one full data-batch will be called a *batch-epoch*. While this distinction between data-batches and mini-batches is normally not relevant since it does not affect the convergence behavior, in this case it provides well-determined mile stones during training for the computation of LRP-heatmap-based metrics after each batch-epoch. Depending on these metrics, we can then employ one of the proposed methods for improving performance on imbalanced datasets (see Sections 6.1, 6.2). This is especially relevant for Section 6.1, where we rebalance the next data-batch according to the LRP-heatmap-based metrics.

To apply LRP to the models and to obtain the LRP-heatmaps our methods and experiments are based on, we utilize the iNNvestigate toolbox (Alber et al., 2019) which offers an easily usable and customizable implementation for various analyzing methods for NNs, including LRP. As suggested for the age and gender classification setting with a VGG-16 model by (Lapuschkin et al., 2017; Lapuschkin, 2019), we use the $\alpha\beta$ -rule with $\alpha = 2, \beta = -1$ for the convolutional layers due to their ReLU activation functions. For the dense layers we employ the ϵ -rule with $\epsilon = 0.01$ to ensure numerical stability of the decomposition. We furthermore apply the \flat -rule to the input layer. This way, invariance to preprocessing-dependent shifts and transformations in the input domain are ensured. This specific combination of LRP-rules was first introduced by (Lapuschkin et al., 2017) and quantified by (Kohlbrenner et

FIGURE 4.1: Batch-wise training procedure. In each *batch-epoch*, a new *data-batch* is selected from the *training partition* according to some rule which depends, e.g., on some LRP-heatmaps generated after the previous batch-epoch. After each batch-epoch, the LRP-heatmaps can be evaluated, e.g., to compute secondary metrics based on them. For the *training* of each batch-epoch, the data-batch is in turn split into *mini-batches* that are then used for mini-batch gradient descent in a common manner.

al., 2019) as the best variant for the VGG-16 model in computer-vision applications.

4.2 Evaluation Methods

As stated in Chapter 1, we aim to equalize NN performance on imbalanced datasets based on LRP. To measure this performance, we employ different evaluation metrics.

Usually for NNs the generalization performance is estimated using the test set prediction accuracy, i.e., the percentage of correctly predicted samples from the test set (containing data previously unseen by the network):

$$\text{acc} = \frac{|\{i | p_i = c_i\}|}{n} \quad (4.1)$$

where for test samples $\{i\}$, $i \in \{1, \dots, n\}$, the predicted labels are denoted as $\{p_i\}$ and the true labels as $\{c_i\}$. In multi-class settings, often a top-n-accuracy is used additionally, considering not only the true class, but also other classes for each sample. As a special case of this measure, a one-off-accuracy where the true class and adjacent ones are considered, is often applied to the Adience dataset, as its (age) classes are labeled ordinally. Here, predictions for this purpose are usually obtained utilizing all ten crops per test image, as introduced by (Levi and Hassner, 2015), allowing for a simple and comparable estimation of the networks' generalization performance. However, for imbalanced datasets, this measure can fail to produce a good estimation, since it depends on the class distribution of the test set. For many face recognition datasets, e.g., Adience, the true generalized class distribution is very different from the dataset class distribution, i.e., true demographics vs. the age class distribution in the dataset. Thus the test set accuracy may estimate the true generalization performance very poorly, as majority classes may be overrepresented and minority classes underrepresented.

For a fairer evaluation, the accuracy can be measured class-wise on the test set, and then averaged to an overall estimate. However, accuracy is not a good metric to monitor the whole training process since, especially in the beginning of training,

the network tends to strongly overfit to one majority class (Guo et al., 2008), i.e., to classify every sample as belonging to the largest class, resulting in a high accuracy for this class, even though a discriminative understanding is not demonstrated. For this reason, we also employ the (averaged) class-wise F1 score, i.e.,

$$\begin{aligned}
 \text{prec}_c &= \frac{|\{i|p_i = c, c_i = c\}|}{|\{i|p_i = c\}|} \\
 \text{rec}_c &= \frac{|\{i|p_i = c, c_i = c\}|}{|\{i|c_i = c\}|} \\
 \text{F1}_c &= 2 \cdot \frac{\text{prec}_c \cdot \text{rec}_c}{\text{prec}_c + \text{rec}_c} \\
 \text{F1} &= \frac{1}{|C|} \sum_{c=0}^C \text{F1}_c
 \end{aligned} \tag{4.2}$$

where $c \in \{1, \dots, C\}$ denotes a class label of the dataset. This metric offers independence from the class distribution of the test set since all classes contribute equally. Furthermore, it estimates the performance of a single class in a more reliable fashion than the accuracy-based metrics, even in the beginning of the training process. Thus, during the experiments, this is the most representative metric for comparing the LRP-heatmap-based measures.

Chapter 5

Validating LRP-Heatmaps as a Measure of Understanding

As discussed in Section 2.3, the heatmaps generated by LRP can offer insights into how a deep neural network (NN) arrives at its decisions. For the purpose of this thesis, we plan on exploiting these heatmaps to measure how well a network understands and represents the data. But to be able to employ them in this way, we first need to ascertain whether these heatmaps offer a valid estimation of the networks' generalization performance. In this context, note the difference between *understanding* and *performance*: While the traditional metrics detailed in Section 4.2 measure the *performance* of a NN, i.e., the correctness of its predictions, we assume that the LRP-heatmaps offer information about the NN's *understanding* of the data, i.e., how surely it can distinguish various classes from each other. However, as we ultimately aim to achieve a more balanced classification *performance* on imbalanced data in Chapter 6 by utilizing LRP-heatmaps, we aim to explore how the notion of *understanding* measured by them and the NN's *performance* are connected.

5.1 Setup and Method

For this purpose, we propose a cross-validation setting for age and gender estimation: We divide the dataset into a training and a test partition (90% train, 10% test). We then split the *training set* into four folds and perform parameter selection for different learning rates (0.00006, 0.00008, 0.00010, 0.00012, 0.00014) via hold-one-out cross-validation. For this experiment we do not adhere to the proposed folds in the Adience dataset, but instead combine all these folds into one partition to split into training, test, and validation sets to gain more flexibility in choosing the cross-validation parameters. While this may result in images of the same person being represented in all three sets, and thus in an overestimation of the networks' generalization performance of *age classification*, it does not affect the possible connection between conventional performance metrics and measures based on LRP-heatmaps that we intend to show here.

We first aim to gain information about the relationship between model performance and LRP-heatmap metrics during training. For this purpose, we select 10 random sample images per class from the validation set for each training. From the selected samples, LRP-heatmaps are later computed w.r.t. their predicted class. Thus, we can compare the model performance on the validation set with the LRP-heatmaps of the selected images after each batch-epoch. We assume that the heatmaps obtained from LRP contain information about the networks' understanding of the data, however, as they are very complex, we first need to extract and

quantify this information to be able to make the mentioned comparison. For this purpose, we derive the following higher-level metrics from the heatmaps that offer a comparable estimate of how well and how easily a particular sample is understood by a network. To eliminate any effects of the absolute relevances generally growing larger over the course of training, due to increasing model confidence and the relevance conservation property, we normalize each LRP-heatmap beforehand w.r.t. its largest absolute relevance.

Entropy of LRP-Heatmaps: Firstly, we employ the Shannon-Entropy for this purpose. We compute the LRP-heatmaps of each sample w.r.t. the *predicted* class c_i^t of each sample i at batch-epoch t . As opposed to traditional evaluation metrics that require true class labels, e.g., the F1-score, we thus avoid the restriction of needing labeled data to compute this LRP-heatmap-based measure.

Let $R_{i,c_i^t}^t \in \mathbb{R}^{n \times m}$ be an LRP-heatmap of a sample $i \in \{1 \dots I\}$ w.r.t. the predicted class c_i^t after the model has been trained on batch-epoch $t \in \{1 \dots T\}$. Using LRP-heatmaps w.r.t. the predicted class imposes less constraints compared to LRP-heatmaps w.r.t. the true class of each sample, but does not affect the result of the entropy computation in a meaningful manner under the right conditions (see Figure A.1). Since the relevances in $R_{i,c_i^t}^t$ are continuous, but the entropy is only defined in a discrete space, we encapsulate these relevances uniformly into $B = 256$ bins, with all bins spanning the value range of the respective normalized heatmap. As shown in Figure A.1, this binning produces the most distinctive and concise results. The occurrences $n_b | R_{i,c_i^t}^t$ of each bin b are then counted, where " $|R_{i,c_i^t}^t$ " designates the "given condition of $R_{i,c_i^t}^t$ ", and the probability of occurrence is obtained as

$$p_b(R_{i,c_i^t}^t) = \frac{n_b | R_{i,c_i^t}^t}{n \cdot m} \quad (5.1)$$

The Shannon-Entropy of $R_{i,c_i^t}^t$ is then defined as:

$$H_B(R_{i,c_i^t}^t) = - \sum_b p_b(R_{i,c_i^t}^t) \log_2 p_b(R_{i,c_i^t}^t) \quad (5.2)$$

$H_B(R_{i,c_i^t}^t)$ thus denotes the average information content per bin for the LRP-heatmap $R_{i,c_i^t}^t$. From a theoretical standpoint, a "white noise" heatmap would thus have the highest entropy. In contrast, as a heatmap grows closer towards an impulse, its entropy would decrease. As shown in Figure 5.1, without employing any transfer learning, we observed the LRP-heatmaps to be extremely uniform at the beginning of training (a similar effect was observed by (Samek et al., 2017)), while becoming more fine-grained in the end of the training process, with the former state resulting in a large $H_B(R_{i,c_i^t}^t)$ and the latter in a small $H_B(R_{i,c_i^t}^t)$. Under the assumption that a network which has improved during training has gained a better understanding of the different classes, we can thus infer that LRP-heatmaps w.r.t. better understood classes have a lower entropy than those w.r.t. worse understood classes. This will also be researched experimentally in this Chapter.

Sum of Positive Relevances in LRP-Heatmaps: Positive relevances in LRP-heatmaps denote what speaks *for* a certain class c and how strongly. In contrast, the negative relevances in LRP-heatmaps indicate what speaks *against* c . Thus, in a multi-class-setting, e.g., age classification on the Adience dataset, each LRP-heatmap potentially contains information on *all* classes, not only on c . However, for the purpose of obtaining class-specific information which we require since we plan to utilize

FIGURE 5.1: Changes in LRP-heatmaps over the batch-epochs of the training of a randomly initialized network. Keep in mind that the heatmaps are computed w.r.t. the *predicted* class and rescaled into the interval $[-1, 1]$ while preserving the center point of zero relevance. This is why the relatively uniform heatmaps of the first batch-epoch seem so (globally) relevant but barely show any discriminativity w.r.t. which features are used or ignored. The heatmaps are shown for samples of age classes (*top to bottom*) 0–2, 15–20, 38–43, 60. Here, each single heatmap is normalized w.r.t. its largest absolute relevance, thus removing any influence of the magnitude of the networks’ output. For comparison, the same heatmaps normalized w.r.t. the highest absolute relevance over all batch-epochs can be found in Figure A.2.

this information to improve training behavior on imbalanced data later on (Sections 6.1, 6.2), this property may be a hindrance, as the information on other classes than c potentially distorts information on c . While this issue is easily solved by selecting only the positive relevances, discriminative information is disregarded in doing so, possibly leading to a worse estimation of the networks’ overall understanding, but a better estimation of the networks’ relative understanding of single classes. In addition to utilizing only the positive relevances, which seems promising in determining how well a *single class* is understood by the network at any point, we again only compute LRP-heatmaps w.r.t. the *predicted* class in order to lift the labeling restriction. This measure thus describes how sure the network is of its prediction on a certain sample. In contrast, if the LRP-heatmaps were computed w.r.t. the respective true class, the amount of "truth" in the networks’ decision would be measured. However, in this case, the sum of positive relevances would also include how well a specific sample fits into the learned data manifold, and would thus not be representative for outlier samples. Therefore, the usage of LRP-heatmaps w.r.t. the *predicted* class may not only be the less restricted, but also the more reliable variant.

Formally, we simply sum up the positive relevances in a LRP-heatmap $R_{i,c_i^t}^t = (r_1, \dots, r_m)$ of a sample $i \in \{1 \dots I\}$ w.r.t. the predicted class c_i^t :

$$\sigma(R_{i,c_i^t}^t) = \sum_{k=1}^m \max(0, r_k) \quad (5.3)$$

where a higher value of $\sigma(R_{i,c_i^t}^t)$ should indicate a better understanding of sample i .

MSE-Distance of LRP-Heatmaps: Similarly to the *Entropy of LRP-Heatmaps* and the *Sum of Positive Relevances*, this metric is also derived from LRP-heatmaps. However, it focuses on measuring the convergence of understanding via the amount of change a LRP-heatmap of a constant sample undergoes between two batch-epochs. Because a network that learns to understand the data should be converging, we assume the LRP-heatmaps to generally change quickly in the beginning of the training process and increasingly less towards the end of training. Thus, we reason that quickly converging LRP-heatmaps indicate a better understanding than slower converging heatmaps. For this metric, we again only employ LRP-heatmaps w.r.t. the *predicted* class c_i^t of each sample i . Here, we measure the *change* in the (flattened) LRP-heatmap $R_{i,c_i^t}^t = (x_1^t, \dots, x_m^t)$ of the same sample between two consecutive batch-epochs as pairwise MSE-distances, i.e.,

$$\delta(R_{i,c_i^t}^t) = \frac{1}{m} \sum_{j=1}^m (x_j^t - x_j^{t-1})^2 \quad (5.4)$$

with $\delta(R_{i,c_i^t}^1) = 0$.

We then average these metrics over the different parameters, folds, and samples. Thereafter, we visualize their connection to traditional evaluation metrics described in Section 4.2, and quantify it with the Pearson Correlation Coefficient. To verify and generalize the obtained results we repeat this experiment with different weight initializations and label assignments. The initialization weights can be ordered as follows in terms of prior knowledge specific to the task at hand, i.e., age classification on the Adience dataset: Firstly, Random-initialization offers the least degree of prior knowledge, as no transfer learning is applied. Secondly, weights for the VGG-16 architecture (trained by (Simonyan and Zisserman, 2014)) that were pretrained on the ImageNet dataset (Deng et al., 2009) contain a small degree of prior knowledge, since this dataset offers an image classification setting that is, however, not specific to faces. Thirdly, we utilize initialization weights that were pretrained on the IMDB-WIKI dataset (Rothe, Timofte, and Gool, 2015), which offers face images that are sorted to 101 distinct class labels, different from the Adience dataset. Lastly, we use the final weights achieved by (Lapuschkin et al., 2017) for initialization, which were already pretrained on age classification of the Adience dataset. For readability, we will refer to these four weight initializations as *Random*-initialization, *ImageNet*-initialization, *IMDB-WIKI*-initialization, and *Adience*-initialization in the following. We furthermore explore different multi-class settings by also training on the Adience gender classification task and by merging the eight age class labels of the Adience dataset into either two, three, four, five or eight classes to observe the behavior of the three proposed LRP-based metrics for progressively more complex multi-class settings. Here, we use the weights pretrained on ImageNet for initialization.

5.2 Results and Discussion

Depending on the weight initialization, learning rate parameter, and fold during the cross-validation, the resulting models in this experiment reached average class-wise

TABLE 5.1: Average class-wise traditional generalization performance metrics (accuracy, one-off-accuracy, and F1-score (*top to bottom*)) for the Adience-initialized models and the eight-class age classification task.

Generalization Performance (Adience-Initialization)									
Class (Age)	0–2	4–6	8–13	15–20	25–32	38–43	48–53	60+	Mean
Metric									
Accuracy (%)	64.8	64.8	56.3	36.8	51.3	53.0	28.3	42.0	49.7
One-Off-Accuracy (%)	98.5	97.1	87.6	90.3	93.7	90.7	87.4	70.6	89.5
F1-Score (%)	70.1	59.4	58.0	40.0	43.0	41.2	33.0	51.8	49.6

accuracies of up to 49.7%, average class-wise one-off-accuracies of up to 89.5%, and an average class-wise F1-score of up to 49.6% for the eight-class age classification task. For the detailed performances for the Adience-initialization, see Table 5.1.

5.2.1 Expressivity of LRP-Heatmaps in Comparison to Traditional Evaluation Metrics

Correlation between LRP-heatmap-based metrics and traditional evaluation metrics

The following results show that LRP-heatmaps are at least as expressive as traditional evaluation metrics, e.g., accuracy and F1-score. Moreover, this expressivity can be achieved by LRP-heatmaps without requiring labeled test data, increasing their applicability.

During this experiment, we found strong correlations between the LRP-heatmap-based metrics and the performance of the NN during training, measured in terms of the traditional evaluation metrics, i.e., accuracy, one-off-accuracy, balanced accuracy, and F1-score, as shown in Figure 5.2 for the Adience-initialization. Here, the metrics were measured on the selected validation set samples using Equations (5.2), (5.3), and (5.4) and then averaged over all parameters, folds, and classes. Each datapoint thus denotes the respective average measurements after one of the 100 batch-epochs. While strong and *positive* correlations are apparent between all the LRP-heatmap-based metrics and the network performance, this is — contrary to the *negative* correlation we expected in Section 5.1 — especially the case for the *Entropy of LRP-Heatmaps*, where the datapoints lie on the fitted linear regression line to a large extent, indicating a very strong connection. A few datapoints deviate when compared with accuracy, one-off-accuracy, and balanced accuracy, however, this is not the case for the F1-score which correlates with the entropy almost perfectly (correlation coefficient of 0.98). The latter effect can be attributed to the unreliability of the accuracy measures at the beginning of training, as described in Section 4.2.

FIGURE 5.2: Comparison between (traditional) evaluation metrics and LRP-heatmap-based metrics (Adience-initialization) over training time. Especially the entropy (*top*) and MSE-distance (*bottom*) of LRP-heatmaps have a high correlation to the traditional evaluation metrics. The respective correlation coefficient is denoted as ρ in each sub-figure.

Under the assumption that the F1-score provides a fairer and more complete estimation of the model’s performance — especially of the assumed (population-based) overfitting on the more frequent classes in the imbalanced Adience dataset—, we can furthermore infer that the entropy of LRP-heatmaps also describes the model’s actual performance on the data more truthfully than the accuracy-based measures, as it is on par with the F1-score.

With slight deviations, these results also translate to the ImageNet- and IMDB-WIKI-initializations, where the correlation between the entropy of LRP-heatmaps and traditional metrics is similarly high (see Figure A.4). Interestingly, however, exactly the opposite seems to be true for the Random-initialization, as the correlation is strongly *negative* here (correlation coefficients of -0.95, -0.87, -0.25 respectively of the entropy, sum of positive relevances, and MSE-Distance compared to the F1-score) and aligns with our expectations from Section 5.1. We will discuss this effect in further detail later in this Section.

In contrast to the entropy, the *MSE-Distance of LRP-Heatmaps* shows a weaker correlation (correlation coefficient of 0.93 to F1-score). Especially towards the beginning of training, the MSE-distance deviates from the regression line for the Adience-initialized models (see Figure 5.2). The effect of training seems to be perceptible in the MSE-distance of LRP-heatmaps *even before* the traditional metrics begin to change. In fact, when observing the heatmaps during the first batch-epochs, rapid changes to the heatmaps are immediately visible (Figure 5.3), and this is instantly reflected by the MSE-distance, as this change is what it measures, while traditional

FIGURE 5.3: Changes in the LRP-heatmaps for the batch-epochs in the beginning of training, here shown exemplary for the Adience-initialization and samples of age classes 0–2, 4–6, 25–32, 48–53 (top to bottom). The heatmaps are computed w.r.t. the predicted class. Here, each single heatmap is normalized w.r.t. its largest absolute relevance, thus removing any influence of the magnitude of the networks’ output. The class-specific F1-score and MSE between LRP-heatmaps of the current and previous batch-epochs are denoted above each image, showing that the MSE-distance is able to pick up on small training effects even *before* the F1-score. For comparison, the same heatmaps normalized w.r.t. the highest absolute relevance over all batch-epochs can be found in Figure A.3.

metrics, e.g., the F1-score, take a few batch-epochs more to measure the learning process of the network (Figure A.6), since they are only influenced when samples change the predicted class and, thus, are comparatively coarse measures. This means that the understanding the model gains of the data during training takes some time to reflect in its performance. Thereafter, towards the end of training, the distance and the traditional metrics correlate again. This correlation, however, is not negative for the Adience-initialized models, as we expected in Section 5.1, but positive instead, meaning that the MSE-distance of heatmaps actually increases over the course of training. However, this does again not translate to all four weight initializations (see Figure A.4). For the IMDB-WIKI-initialization, the correlation remains positive, however, it is less pronounced, while for the ImageNet-initialization there barely seems to be any correlation. For the Random-initialization the correlation even becomes negative, thereby aligning with our expectations in Section 5.1. Again, this

effect will be examined more detailed later on.

The *Sum of Positive Relevances in LRP-Heatmaps* does not prove to be correlated to the traditional evaluation metrics as strongly as the entropy or the MSE-distance. In fact, for the Adience-initialization, it deviates from the regression line to a large extent and thus only reaches a correlation coefficient of 0.54 to the F1-score, while the entropy and MSE-Distance reach correlation coefficients of 0.98 and 0.93, respectively. This effect is increasingly pronounced later on during training, where the other metrics converge, while the sum of positive relevances in LRP-heatmaps does not. However, in a way, this aligns with our expectations: While the full heatmaps are used for computing the entropy and MSE-distance of LRP-heatmaps, only the positive parts are utilized for the sum of positive relevances. Thus, the entropy and distance have access to all the information present in the LRP-heatmaps, while the sum of positive relevances only exploits a part of this information, resulting in a worse estimation of the NN’s overall understanding of the data. This deviation, however, is not as pronounced for the other weight initializations. Again, note that for the Random-initialization, the correlation becomes *negative*.

It seems that these results also translate to the class-wise evaluations to some degree, as shown in Figure 5.4 for the Adience-initialized models. This is especially true for the age range 60+, even though the datapoints are a bit more scattered. When comparing LRP-based metrics with the F1-score for the age range 25–32, the previous results also hold, however, for the other metrics, i.e., accuracy and one-off-accuracy, barely any correlation between them and the LRP-based metrics seems to exist (e.g., the entropy has a correlation coefficient of -0.05 to accuracy and one-off-accuracy). However, since the age range 25–32 is by far the largest class in the Adience dataset, this anomaly is easily explained: As already noted in Section 4.2, at the start of training the network begins with predicting most samples as belonging to the largest class(es), in this case, the age range 25–32. This effect, however, leads to the accuracy-based measures starting off extremely high for that class (see Figure 5.5 (left), where age class 25–32 starts with an accuracy of 80%), since they only consider the percentage of correctly predicted samples of it. This, however, does not implicate any understanding, as always predicting the largest class may lead to a relatively high accuracy, but could be done without properly considering the input. The F1-score, on the other hand, even though the described effect is still slightly present, does not start off as high for the largest class(es) (see Figure 5.5 (left), F1-score of 18% for age class 25–32), since it also includes information about false positives, thereby measuring the understanding better than the accuracy.

When applying this information to Figure 5.4, we can thus assume that the LRP-heatmap-based metrics, specifically, the entropy and MSE-distance, are at least on par with the F1-score when it comes to measuring the performance of a network on a certain class. As it performs better than the class-wise accuracy and one-off accuracy in that respect, we thus restrict the comparisons for the LRP-heatmap-based measures in the following to the F1-score. Note that we utilized LRP-heatmaps w.r.t. the *predicted* class for the LRP-heatmap-based metrics, as stated in Section 5.1, thus making them more generally applicable than either the F1-score or the accuracy.

Influence of model variation on the LRP-heatmap-based metrics

In the following, we will show that the results obtained above for the Adience-initialized models generally also hold when employing different initializations that offer a varying degree of previous knowledge about the task:

FIGURE 5.4: Class-wise comparison between (traditional) evaluation metrics and LRP-heatmap-based metrics for the ages 25–32 (left) and 60+ (right) over training time (Adience-initialization). The respective correlation coefficient is denoted as ρ in each subfigure. The general observations made in Figure 5.2 also seem to hold for the single classes. The results for the remaining classes can be found in A.5.

As already stated above, we observed a large discrepancy in the correlation between all three proposed LRP-heatmap-based metrics and traditional evaluation

FIGURE 5.5: Comparison of class-wise accuracy and F1-score over the course of training (Adience-initialization). The lines are smoothed by taking the mean over multiple batch-epochs at each tick. This shows why it is problematic to compare the accuracy to the LRP-heatmap-based metrics, as it does not reflect the understanding of the network correctly during the first batch-epochs. This means that the class-wise accuracy (*left*) is extremely sensitive to the data population problem inherent in the age labels of the Adience dataset.

metrics for different weight initializations (see Figure A.4). Generally speaking, while these correlations usually align with our expectations for the Random-initialization, exactly the opposite seems to be the case to varying degrees when employing transfer learning. Figure 5.6 compares the behavior of the average LRP-heatmap-based metrics and of the average F1-score for the four different weight initializations we employed. Here, we observe that the models utilizing transfer learning achieve a relatively similar F1-score (*top left*, 49%, 47%, and 43% for the Adience-, IMDB-WIKI-, and Imagenet-initialized models, respectively), however, the F1-score of the randomly initialized models is far lower (F1-score of 31%) and does not seem to converge over the course of the executed batch-epochs. In a similar manner, the LRP-heatmap-based metrics apparently register this difference between Random-initialization and the other weight initializations. E.g., the *Entropy of LRP-Heatmaps* (see Figure 5.6 (*top right*)) is more than twice as large for the models that use Random-initialization as for the models employing transfer learning. The randomly initialized models behave as expected, with the entropy decreasing over time, as the heatmaps grow progressively less uniform (see Figure 5.1). Concurrently, the F1-score increases, indicating that a lower entropy implicates a better understanding. This is further supported by the better performing models (orange, red, green) having a lower entropy. However, when only considering the models that use transfer learning, this observation does not seem to hold: In fact, their average entropy of LRP-heatmaps *increases* over the course of training. Also, the best models (red) have a higher average entropy than the slightly worse models (green, orange). Nevertheless, an explanation for this phenomenon is provided when considering the heatmaps of these models (e.g., Figure 5.7): Their initial heatmaps are not very uniform, resulting in the low entropy at the beginning. In fact, as can be observed, e.g., for the IMDB-WIKI-initialization, over the first few batch-epochs the relevance of single pixels increases disproportionately, showing that the model uses these single (pre-learned) pixels rather than larger descriptive features to decide on a class. As the LRP-heatmaps grow closer to an impulse for these first batch-epochs,

FIGURE 5.6: Average metrics for different weight initializations over batch-epochs. The metrics depicted are the F1-score (*top left*), the entropy of LRP-heatmaps (*top right*), the sum of positive relevances in LRP-heatmaps (*bottom left*, logscale), and the MSE-distance of LRP-heatmaps (*bottom right*). While the metrics behave relatively similar for networks that utilize transfer learning (*orange, green, red*), for the randomly initialized models (*blue*) they behave differently for all three LRP-heatmap-based metrics (*top right, bottom left, bottom right*).

the average entropy of LRP-heatmaps then decreases (as expected), however, the strong focus on singular pixels is not desirable and indicates overfitting. Thus, a large entropy seems to indicate a missing understanding of the data, as very uniform heatmaps show that no features are particularly relevant. In contrast, a heatmap that is not uniform enough, i.e., close to an impulse, indicates that the model overfits on single pixels and considers them overly important, instead of using descriptive features to make decisions. The "optimal" heatmaps would thus be neither too uniform nor too similar to localized impulses. With this perspective, the entropy seems to converge toward that theoretical optimum for all models, explaining its different directionalities even though the F1-score increases for all models. This further explains the high F1-score of the models using the Adience-initialization, as their entropy of LRP-heatmaps seems to be closest to the theoretical optimum.

The *Sum of Positive Relevances in LRP-Heatmaps* behave similarly to the entropy: Since we normalize the LRP-heatmaps before computing the sum of positive relevances, they also measure the uniformity of the heatmap and are sensitive to the

FIGURE 5.7: Changes in LRP-heatmaps over the batch-epochs of the training of an ImageNet-initialized network (*top*), IMDB-WIKI-initialized network (*middle*), and Adience-initialized network (*bottom*). The heatmaps are computed w.r.t. the *predicted* class and normalized into the interval $[-1, 1]$. Note the overfitting effect between heatmaps of batch-epochs 1 and 10, where single isolated (pre-learned) features are used for prediction, especially visible for the IMDB-WIKI-initialization (*middle*).

same overfitting effect we described above. Here, however, only the positive relevances in a LRP-heatmap are taken into consideration, explaining the fast decrease of this measure during the first batch-epochs for the randomly initialized models (see Figure 5.6 *bottom left*), as some pixels quickly become negatively relevant.

In contrast to the previous two metrics that consider the *uniformity* of LRP-heatmaps from different perspectives, the *MSE-Distance of LRP-Heatmaps* measures the *convergence* of the respective models. In Section 5.1 we expected this distance to decrease over the course of training with the models converging, a behavior that seems to apply at least for the randomly initialized models (see Figure 5.6 *bottom right*): For these models (blue curve), the distance rapidly increases in the beginning (11 at batch-epoch 1 and 16 at batch-epoch 15)— an effect that can again be attributed to the appearance of negative relevances during those batch-epochs — but then decreases steadily (to 10 at batch-epoch 99), in alignment with our expectation. However, with increasing prior knowledge offered by the initialization weights, this assumption seems to apply progressively less. For the ImageNet-initialized models, the MSE-distance only decreases slightly (6 at batch-epoch 15 and 5 at batch-epoch 99), explaining the barely existing correlation to the traditional metrics we found in Figure A.4. For the IMDB-WIKI-initialized models and even more for the Adience-initialized models the distance increases instead (4 at batch-epoch 15 and 5 at batch-epoch 99 for the Adience-initialized models). One possible interpretation for this phenomenon is that the models initialized with more prior knowledge already start near a local optimum, with consecutive mini-batch gradient descent steps going in varying directions with a low momentum — explaining the low starting MSE-distance. However, during training, the distance becomes *relatively* larger as a good optimization direction is found — albeit it still stays far smaller *absolutely* than for the randomly initialized models —, until the model starts converging near a different local optimum. At this point the distance would then decrease again,

FIGURE 5.8: Class-wise comparison between F1-score and LRP-heatmap-based metrics for all eight classes over training time (Adience-initialization). For all classes and metrics, a positive correlation to the F1-score seems to exist, albeit to a varying degree. Note that the classes are grouped and quite easily separable along both axes, indicating a (negative) between-class correlation between F1-score and LRP-heatmap-based metrics.

resulting in its overall concave behavior. The better the initialization in terms of previous knowledge and the more complex the task, the longer it would thus take the model to reach that point of beginning convergence, i.e., decreasing MSE-distance of LRP-heatmaps, an assertion that is supported by Figures 5.6/A.10 and Figure A.14, respectively.

5.2.2 Comparison between Class-wise Behavior of LRP-Heatmaps and Traditional Evaluation metrics

Class-wise behavior of LRP-heatmap-based metrics

Next, we will analyze whether the class-wise measurements of the LRP-heatmap-based metrics can be utilized to indicate how well and in which order the single classes separate, a prerequisite for Chapter 6. In the following paragraphs, we will show that this class-wise ordering is extremely close to that suggested by the class-wise F1-score:

In Figures 5.2 and 5.4 we generally found large correlations between the metrics based on LRP-heatmaps and traditional evaluation metrics. Figure 5.8, however, shows a different effect for the Adience-initialized models: Here, the metrics based on LRP-heatmaps were again measured on the selected samples and then, for each (true) class, averaged over all parameters and folds. While the general results up to this point were obtained without the need for labeled data, for the class-wise results from here on, access to the true labels thus is, in fact, required. However, the following analyses are performed with the goal in mind to apply the class-wise measures for making class-wise alterations to the networks' training process in Chapter 6, where labeled data is already a prerequisite. While for some classes (e.g., ages 15–20) the same positive correlation between LRP-heatmap-based measures and F1-score that was visible in Figures 5.2 and 5.4 is found, this correlation seems to barely exist for other classes, e.g., ages 0–2 or 48–53, at least for a small F1-score. Furthermore, we also notice that the measurements are grouped and even ordered very distinctively for the different classes. However, the order of these class-groups that is suggested by the F1-score is largely reversed by the ordering suggested by the metrics based on LRP-heatmaps. More concisely, while the overall and class-wise trend of the LRP-heatmap-based metrics is largely the same as for the F1-score, i.e., a *positive* correlation exists (see Figures 5.2, 5.4), the between-class trend seems to be

FIGURE 5.9: Class-wise progression of LRP-heatmap-based metrics (Adience-initialization). The lines are smoothed, the original data can be found in the Appendix, Figures A.8, A.9, A.10 (bottom right). The classes separate quite well, albeit in the reverse order as given by the F1-score (Figure 5.5 (right)). Note the overfitting effect that is especially present for the better performing classes (0–2, 4–6, 8–13) in the beginning of training.

reversed, i.e., correlated *negatively*. While the first part of this result did not align with our expectations (Section 5.1), the second part does.

An explanation for this phenomenon, however, is offered upon closer inspection of how the class-wise LRP-heatmap-based metrics change on average over the course of training for Adience-initialized models (Figure 5.9). For the entropy of LRP-heatmaps, we find that for classes that the network learns to predict relatively accurately according to the F1-score (see Figure 5.5 (right) for reference), the entropy starts off in a decreasing manner, with a negative correlation to the F1-score (e.g., a correlation coefficient of -0.78 for ages 0–2, and -0.89 for ages 4–6 until batch-epoch 17 which we chose representatively for the batch-epochs 15–20). However, for classes with a lower F1-score, e.g., ages 15–20 and 38–43, the entropy increases in the beginning, with a positive correlation coefficient to the F1-score, i.e., 0.81 for ages 15–20 and 0.43 for ages 38–43 until batch-epoch 17. After this divergence, however, the

entropy increases for all classes around batch-epochs 15–20, which is where the F1-score on the test set generally also starts to increase, resulting in a positive correlation to the F1-score for all classes (e.g., a correlation coefficient of 0.20 for ages 0–2, 0.64 for ages 4–6, 0.88 for ages 15–20, and 0.77 for ages 38–43 during batch-epochs 18–100). The result of Equation (5.2) grows larger the more equally the relevances are distributed and decreases when this distribution grows closer to an impulse.

For instance, the entropy of a LRP-heatmap would increase for a uniformly distributed heatmap. In turn, it would decrease if the number of relevant pixels decreases, or single pixels become disproportionately more relevant. In fact, this overfitting effect that we already described in Figure 5.7 is exactly what we can observe in Figure 5.3: E.g., for the sample of class 4–6, all features except for eyes, nose, and mouth become comparatively irrelevant within the first ten batch-epochs. Even within these three features, single pixels start to overshadow the other parts, bringing the value-distribution of this heatmap closer to an impulse. This overfitting, however, mainly seems to happen for relatively easily learnable classes, i.e., classes that the model can distinguish from others quite well using only few and small features. These features would be found quickly by the network, kept relatively static, and their relevance would be strengthened. For classes whose discriminative features are more complex and not as easily accessible to the model, however, relevance would not be assigned only to singular pixels or features in the first batch-epochs, but instead distributed more equally across a larger number of pixels and various features, leading to rapidly changing heatmaps and an increase in entropy instead. This phenomenon can be observed in Figure 5.3, e.g., for age classes 0–2 vs. 48–53. With the focus on single pixels not being sufficient and understanding of other classes increasing, the relevance assignment would then also grow more uniformly distributed for the easily learnable classes (compare, e.g., batch-epochs 10 and 16 for age class 4–6 in Figure 5.3), leading to the entropy rising again, even though the relative ordering of classes remains the same. While a comparatively low entropy seems to imply a good performance and understanding of that class, a high entropy does not necessarily seem to imply a bad performance and understanding (see age class 60+). This means that for classes which can be distinguished from others using small and few features, these features seem to also be easily learnable by the model. However, the more complex features of classes that are not as easily distinguishable are not necessarily difficult to learn. But, as the age class 60+ is an edge case, this might also be the reason for it being relatively easy for the network to distinguish from other classes.

This notion is additionally supported by the sum of positive relevances in LRP-heatmaps (Figure 5.9 (*top right*)). As the heatmaps are normalized to compute the proposed metrics, the focused strengthening of the positive relevance of single pixels in the beginning would lead to a decrease in the sum of positive relevances. This effect seems to be stronger for better performing classes, possibly because the network finds a relatively small but good set of features early. The LRP-heatmaps for these classes would not change as much — evidence which is further supported by Figure 5.9 (*bottom left*), as described in the following paragraph. This results in the same pixels being assigned an increasingly high relevance in the beginning, leading to an overall *decrease* in the (normalized) sum of positive relevances. This decrease seems to happen for all classes, though later and to a smaller degree for more difficult classes, which would further support the idea that the network has more trouble understanding these classes and finding a good representation for them. Again, for all classes a relatively constant increase in the sum of positive relevances happens around batch-epoch 20, depending on the class.

The relation between classes according to the MSE-distance of LRP-heatmaps, however, behaves as expected (Figure 5.9 (bottom right)): At first, the distance starts growing for all classes, i.e., the heatmaps change increasingly. Starting at batch-epoch 13, however, the classes diverge, with the distance not growing larger or even decreasing (e.g., class 0-2: decrease from 2.6 at batch-epoch 15 to 1.7 at batch-epoch 25) before increasing steadily for the better performing classes (e.g., class 0-2: increase to 2.8 at batch-epoch 99), while only rising for the worse performing classes. This means that the heatmaps of classes which are more easily understood by the network do not change as rapidly during training as the heatmaps of classes that are not comprehended as easily, since the features that describe an easily understood class well seem to be found relatively quickly and kept comparatively static by the network. However, a slow increase of the MSE-distance still happens for all classes from around batch-epoch 25, explaining the positive overall correlation to the traditional metrics in Figure 5.2.

In contrast to the traditional metrics in Figure 5.5, we also note that the LRP-heatmap-based metrics do not reflect a bias towards majority classes in the beginning of training, as we observed above for the accuracy and, to a lesser degree, the F1-score.

A possible explanation for the class-wise behavior of all three metrics would be that in a first learning phase, the network finds a baseline of features defining each class, with this step taking a few batch-epochs longer for more difficult classes, and the feature description not being as unique and definite as for more easily understood classes. This step would result in the starting divergence between classes observed for all three LRP-based metrics. When this baseline description is found, these features would then be finetuned at around the same rate for each class, leading to a relatively constant, small increase for all three metrics. This second step would also coincide with the F1-score on the test set starting to increase (see Figure 5.5 (right)). The divergence of metrics, their starting decrease, and the following increase of some classes explain why the correlation between LRP-based metrics and F1-score varies so much across classes in Figure 5.8.

For the class-wise F1-score and all three LRP-heatmap-based metrics the above assertions in terms of the class-wise ordering that were made for the Adience-initialization also hold for the ImageNet- and IMDB-WIKI-initialization (see Figures A.7, A.8, A.9, and A.10). However, for the randomly initialized models (top left), this ordering seems to be reversed in comparison. But, upon closer inspection, the class-wise order here changes over the course of training, with the classes with a higher F1-score decreasing with a steeper slope than classes with a lower F1-score. While this effect exists for all three LRP-heatmap-based metrics, it is especially pronounced for the *MSE-Distance of LRP-Heatmaps* (Figure A.10), where, e.g., class 0-2 (blue) moves from achieving one of the highest MSE-distance to having the lowest MSE-distance over the course of training. As this phenomenon appears very consistently for all three LRP-heatmap-based metrics, but only for the randomly initialized models, a possible interpretation would be that under these circumstances the class-wise differences are not as pronounced in the beginning, since the overall performance is too low for them to be reflected. However, as the randomly initialized model learns, the overall performance increases and stronger class-wise differences develop.

Influence of task variation on the LRP-heatmap-based metrics

Finally, we will show that the results obtained above even largely hold when varying the classification task of the model, by classifying for gender instead of age and by varying the number of age classes:

To confirm the above results over different classification tasks, we trained Adience-initialized models on the age classification task with a modified number of age classes and on the gender classification task. The results of this verification are shown in Figures A.11 - A.14. The results we previously obtained above for the eight-class age classification task also seem to hold for all other non-binary classification settings. For binary classification, however, this does not seem to be the case. Here, the class with the (marginally) better F1-score seems to also achieve a higher entropy of LRP-heatmaps (Figure A.12 *top*) than the other class. As binary classification is a comparatively easy task, a decision against one class is automatically a decision for the other class, and the F1-score of both classes is extremely close (Figure A.11 *top*, e.g., "male" and "female" both reach a F1-score of 95% for the gender classification *top left*). However, the heatmaps of the two classes are quite dissimilar, as shown in Figure A.15 (*two left columns*) for the gender classification task: The heatmaps for the class "male" contain less negative relevances than those of the class "female" — resulting in a lower entropy of the class "male". While the reason for this phenomenon may be the choice of randomly selected samples per class, the entropy for two age class labels behaves in a similar manner, indicating that it happens, in fact, due to the binary classification setting. While the positive relevances of the "female" class seem to still outweigh the negative relevances, the increased negative relevances compared to the "male" class indicate a higher insecurity for the class "female" — even though this insecurity is not necessarily reflected in the final decisions. Under that assumption, the heatmaps provided by LRP, and, by extension, the *Entropy of LRP-Heatmaps*, seem to offer a better indication of the actual *understanding* a network has of a certain class, as opposed to the *generalization performance* measured by traditional metrics.

Due to the normalization of heatmaps, the *Sum of Positive Relevances* behaves in a similar manner as the entropy, however, Figure A.13 indicates an issue inherent to that measure. While for gender classification, the sum behaves similar to the entropy, for two-age-class classification it does not. The class "older" contains a lot more negative relevances than positive ones (see Fig. A.15 (*two right columns*)). Even though these heatmaps were computed w.r.t. the respective predicted class, they contain far more negative relevances than positive ones. However, for the models we used, the biases in the last layer were not kept at zero, but learned instead, resulting in a negative bias (-0.01) for class "younger" and a positive bias (+0.01) for class "older". When employing LRP, relevance is "lost" to the biases (Lapuschkin, 2019), and, especially in the case of binary age classification, this seems to lead to mainly negative heatmaps w.r.t. the predicted class, especially for a positive bias. Since the sum of positive relevances only considers positive relevances, this leads to a lower sum for that class, indicating that the sum of positive relevances may be too prone to noisiness, thus being a relatively unreliable measure. The class-wise *MSE-Distance of LRP-Heatmaps* (Figure A.14) for the binary classification settings (*top*) does not diverge much between classes, and thus behaves the most similar measure to the F1-score. In comparison, when not using biases in the last layer, this effect does not occur and the LRP-heatmap-based metrics behave as expected even for the binary classification (see Figure A.16).

While the general trend of the three proposed metrics is often reversed compared to our expectations, the ordering of classes is not, at least in a multi-class setting, and, upon further inspection the behavior of all three metrics is explainable for different models and label assignments. Thus, they provide a *relative* class ordering during training that seems to imply how well the network understands the different classes and exhibits a connection to the networks' class-wise performance. As such, the idea of using these three metrics to compute class-wise weights for the purpose of resampling the data-batches (see Section 6.1) or scaling the class-wise losses (see Section 6.2) appears promising.

Key Insights

- We found a strong correlation between LRP-heatmap-based metrics and traditional evaluation metrics, showing that LRP-heatmaps are at least as expressive as traditional evaluation metrics, e.g., accuracy and F1-score.
- While these traditional evaluation metrics require labeled test data, the proposed LRP-heatmap-based metrics do not and can thus measure understanding and indicate performance even if only unlabeled test data is available.
- The metrics based on LRP-heatmaps show a clear class-wise separability and ordering that correlates to that of the class-wise F1-score, indicating that LRP-heatmaps and the metrics based on them are promising for making class-wise adaptations to the training process in order to make the network consider imbalanced classes in a fairer manner.
- These results generally hold across different models and tasks.

Chapter 6

Improving Classification Performance on Imbalanced Data

6.1 Batch Resampling

Inspired by the *Data-focused* approaches described in Section 2.2, we first aim to re-balance the distribution of the data that is fed to the network. For this purpose, we employ an approach that is a combination of oversampling and undersampling and depends on class-wise weights which can be computed from various metrics, e.g., LRP-heatmaps.

6.1.1 Setup and Method

For this experiment, the division of the training process into batch-epochs is especially important, as it allows for data resampling on the larger data-batches. Let n_c be the number of available training samples $\{S_c\}$ for a given class $c \in \{1 \dots C\}$. We then interpret the class-wise weights w_c^t as the percentage of the data-batch at batch-epoch $t \in \{1 \dots T\}$ that should consist of samples from class c . More precisely, for each data-batch, $\lceil w_c^t \cdot l_d \rceil$ samples are randomly selected from $\{S_c\}$ for each class c with l_d denoting a parameter defining the length of these data-batches. Should $\{S_c\}$ contain less than $\lceil w_c^t \cdot l_d \rceil$ datapoints, some samples may be selected more than once. While this potential repetition of datapoints introduces its own problems, e.g., overfitting (see Section 2.2), we do not artificially create datapoints, since the corresponding methods are not reliably applicable to highly complex image data.

The class-wise weights w_c^t can theoretically be obtained in any way, as long as they lie in the interval $[0, 1]$, since they represent percentages. In practice, we restrict them to the interval $]0, 1[$ to guarantee that each data-batch contains samples of all classes. For the first batch epoch, we initialize $\forall c : w_c^1 = \frac{1}{C}$, as there are usually no measurements available yet. For all other batch-epochs, we calculate the class-wise weights on-line during training from the following metrics, three of which were already introduced in Chapter 5. As that experiment confirmed a strong correlation between these three LRP-heatmap-based metrics and the performance of a NN during training, it seems feasible to base the computation of the class-wise weights on them.

Entropy of LRP-Heatmaps: After the network has completed the training of an arbitrary batch-epoch $t \in \{1, \dots, T\}$, we obtain the class-wise weights $w_c^{t+1} \in]0, 1[$ from Equation (5.2). They should reflect the relationship between the entropy of the LRP-heatmap w.r.t. a class and the network's understanding of this class. I.e., in order

to improve the performance on less understood classes, according to our findings in Chapter 5, a small entropy should correspond to a small weight and a large entropy to a large weight. Given a series of LRP-heatmaps (R_{i,c_i}^t) for samples $i \in \{1, \dots, I\}$ w.r.t. the predicted class c_i^t of the respective samples each, we calculate the class-wise weights by first applying Equation (5.2) to every LRP-heatmap in (R_{i,c_i}^t) , and then compute the class-wise average w.r.t. the true class tr_i :

$$H_c^t = \frac{1}{|\{i|tr_i = c\}|} \sum_{j \in \{i|tr_i = c\}} H_B(R_{j,c_j}^t) \quad (6.1)$$

where $c \in \{1, \dots, C\}$ denotes a class label. We choose the samples according to their true class labels instead of their predicted class labels because only then we can guarantee $\forall c : |\{i|tr_i = c\}| > 0$. For each class c , the values in H_c^t are then transformed into the interval $]0, 1[$ by computing the L1-norm over all H_c^t to yield the final class weights w_c^{t+1} of the next batch-epoch.

Sum of Positive Relevances in LRP-Heatmaps: Here, we obtain the class-wise weights $w_c^{t+1} \in]0, 1[$ for the next batch-epoch using Equation (5.3). For this purpose, we first need to estimate the network's understanding of the data in a class-wise manner. To guarantee equal representation of each class c , we can again select the samples according to their true label. For a series of LRP-heatmaps (R_{i,c_i}^t) of some samples i after batch-epoch t , we apply Equation (5.3) to every LRP-heatmap in (R_{i,c_i}^t) and average class-wise w.r.t. the true class tr_i , obtaining an estimate of the network's understanding of c as

$$S_c^t = \frac{1}{|\{i|tr_i = c\}|} \sum_{j \in \{i|tr_i = c\}} \sigma(R_{j,c_j}^t) \quad (6.2)$$

Again, to obtain the final class weights w_c^{t+1} , for each class c , the values S_c^t are transformed into the interval $]0, 1[$. This measure S_c^t is insofar different from the Shannon-Entropy of LRP-heatmaps, as it is possibly more accurate for distinguishing the different classes, since the entropy measures the information content of the heatmap, possibly including more information on all classes to a varying degree. We can thus assume that the entropy tends to measure the *general* understanding that the network has of the data, while the sum of positive relevances tends to include the *class-specific* understanding of the network to a higher degree.

MSE-Distance of LRP-Heatmaps: In a similar manner as for the two previously discussed metrics, we apply Equation (5.4) to a series of LRP-heatmaps (R_{i,c_i}^t) of some samples i after batch-epoch t in order to compute the weights. We then take the class-wise average w.r.t. the true class tr_i , i.e.,

$$D_c^t = \frac{1}{|\{i|tr_i = c\}|} \sum_{j \in \{i|tr_i = c\}} \delta(R_{j,c_j}^t) \quad (6.3)$$

Afterwards, we obtain the final weights w_c^{t+1} for each class c , by transforming the values D_c^t into the interval $]0, 1[$.

Data Distribution: To make a comparison with a metric that does not depend on LRP-heatmaps, we here use the training data distribution in order to attain class-wise weights $w_c^t \in]0, 1[$. For this purpose, since we want less represented classes to receive a higher weight than better represented classes, we divide the number of

samples n in the training dataset by the number of samples n_c of each class c . After transforming the results into the interval $]0, 1[$ for each class c , we obtain the weights $w_c^{data} \in]0, 1[$. For comparability with the other metrics, we keep w_c^1 initialized as $\forall c : w_c^1 = \frac{1}{c}$. However, as the data distribution does not depend on the NN's training progress in any way, we here gain the class-wise weights for each following batch-epoch as $\forall t \geq 2 : w_c^t = w_c^{data}$.

After we have shown in Section 5 that a strong relationship exists between the generalization performance of a network and metrics based on LRP-heatmaps, we will apply and compare the above ways of obtaining class-wise weights during the following experiment in terms of improving the neural network (NN) training process on imbalanced data, i.e., the Adience benchmark dataset.

For this experiment, we again select 10 random sample images per class from the test set. With a data-batch size of 10,000, we then train the network for 100 batch-epochs, applying the method described above. We use equal class-wise weights initially for the first batch-epoch, however, after that, we compute LRP-heatmaps for the selected samples at each batch-epoch, apply one of the described metrics to obtain the class-wise weights, and finally build the next data-batch according to these weights.

This experiment is repeated for all the above metrics, i.e., the entropy of LRP-heatmaps, the sum of positive relevances in LRP-heatmaps, the MSE-distance of LRP-heatmaps, and the training data distribution. For the first three metrics, the class-wise weights change with every batch-epoch, for the last one they stay constant. For the entropy and sum of positive relevances we also experiment with LRP-heatmaps of samples drawn both from the training and test set, to ascertain whether there is a difference in performance. We furthermore train a baseline for comparison with no class-wise weights at all, where the training set is directly decomposed into data-batches.

For each of the described sets of parameters, we train 5 models (i.e., we repeat our series of experiments five times) to increase the stability of the results.

6.1.2 Results and Discussion

Average performance of different methods to obtain class-wise weights for recomposing data-batches

Upon initial inspection, the results obtained in this experiment do not seem very promising, as shown in Figure 6.1. Here, the average accuracy (*left*) and F1-score (*right*) are shown over batch-epochs for each metric we employed to compute the class-wise weights. It seems that only the batch resampling based on the distribution of the training data, while not achieving a better performance than the baseline in the end, drastically increases the convergence speed of the network (F1-score of 43.9% at batch-epoch 25 when using the training data distribution, while the baseline has only reached 33.6%). In contrast, the class-wise weights based on the three suggested LRP-heatmap-metrics seem to lead to a worse performance, especially for the MSE-distance of LRP-heatmaps. They converge much slower (e.g., when using the MSE-distance only an F1-score of 30.2 % is reached at batch-epoch 25) and do not even reach the final F1-score of the baseline models. Up to this point, it seems that resampling the data-batch according to class-wise weights obtained from metrics based on LRP-heatmaps in fact decreases the networks' performance.

TABLE 6.1: Average class-wise traditional generalization performance metrics (accuracy, one-off-accuracy, and F1-score (*top to bottom*)) for the ImageNet-initialized baseline models.

Generalization Performance									
Class (Age)	0–2	4–6	8–13	15–20	25–32	38–43	48–53	60+	Mean
Metric									
Accuracy (%)	57.5	61.2	75.5	22.8	57.6	50.4	28.2	39.9	49.1
One-Off-Accuracy (%)	96.7	96.2	92.7	90.1	91.3	88.3	87.0	70.1	89.1
F1-Score (%)	66.4	58.3	69.0	28.7	43.3	40.2	32.8	50.4	48.6

FIGURE 6.1: Average accuracy (*left*) and F1-score (*right*) for the batch resampling based on different metrics. Here, it seems that only the batch resampling based on the training data distribution (*red*) leads to any performance improvement, i.e., achieving a similar performance as the baseline, but faster. In contrast, the LRP-heatmap-based methods, especially when utilizing the MSE-distance of LRP-heatmaps (*green*) seem to result in a worse overall performance than the baseline. However, keep in mind that the goal we aimed to achieve was not to obtain higher performances, but instead, to balance the class-wise performances.

FIGURE 6.2: Performance comparison of the various metrics that are utilized for re-sampling the data-batches during training. The results for the three metrics based on LRP-heatmaps, i.e., entropy, sum of positive relevances, and MSE-distance are visualized by the *blue*, *orange*, and *green* lines, respectively. The performance of the batch-rebalancing using the distribution of the training data is shown in *red*, while the baseline, i.e., not adapting the training process in any way, is shown in *purple*. This comparison is visualized for ages 8–13 (*left*) and 48–53 (*right*), results for the other ages are depicted in Figure A.17. The average class-wise F1-score is employed as a measure of performance. Note that, while the LRP-heatmap-based methods, especially when utilizing the MSE-distance, result in a lower F1-score on better performing classes, e.g., ages 8–13, they in turn achieve a far higher F1-score than the baseline models or the models employing training-distribution-based batch resampling on worse performing classes, e.g., ages 48–53.

Class-wise performance when using different methods to obtain class-wise weights for recomposing data-batches

Nevertheless, when taking a closer look at the behavior of the networks' performance on single age classes for the different metrics over the course of training (Figure 6.2), the above assertion does not seem to hold: For classes on which the baseline network performed well, e.g., class 8–13 (see Table 6.1 for reference), the class-wise weights based on LRP-heatmap-metrics decrease the F1-score of the network, compared with the baseline. In contrast, for the classes on which the baseline models achieve a very low F1-score, e.g., class 48–53, the networks' performance actually *increases* compared to the baseline (Figure 6.2 *right*). For the baseline models, the F1-score of this class does not even increase until batch-epoch 19, and only reaches a final F1-score of 27.9%. However, when altering the data-batch composition, the network seems to learn to distinguish that class earlier, i.e., at batch-epoch 11 for the weights based on the distribution of the training data. For the weights based on LRP-heatmap-metrics, the F1-score of that class even begins to increase *immediately* at the start of training and converge much faster. Note that the weights based on the MSE-distance of LRP-heatmaps (*green*), while seeming to achieve the worst overall F1-score in Figure 6.1, manages to perform best on the previously worst class 48–53, with a F1-score of 30.2%. In summary, a trade-off seems to exist for the class-wise

FIGURE 6.3: Progression of the class-wise F1-score (smoothed) for the baseline models (*top left*), and for the models where batch resampling was applied during training. The original data can be found in Figure A.18. The results for using the distribution of the training data as a basis for this method are visualized in the (*top right*) and for the three LRP-heatmap-based metrics, i.e., entropy, sum of positive relevances, and MSE-distance in the (*middle left*), (*middle right*), and (*bottom*), respectively. The black lines indicate the lowest and highest class-wise performances at the last batch-epoch for each method. For each of these variations, the variance of average class-wise F1-scores at batch-epoch 100 is marked as σ^2 . Note that all metrics for these results were computed from training samples. In comparison to the baseline models, the training-distribution-based batch resampling achieved the same performance slightly faster. The LRP-heatmap-based methods, however, managed to force the network towards a far more balanced class-wise performance (see the lower variance σ^2 at batch-epoch 100 for the LRP-heatmap-based metrics and the lower distance between lowest and highest performance), considering all classes similarly from the start (refer to the original data in Figure A.18).

TABLE 6.2: Deviations from the baseline at batch-epoch 45 of the class-wise F1-scores for the four employed variations of batch resampling, i.e., about midway through training. The batch resampling based on the distribution of the training data improves on all classes in comparison to the baseline. In contrast, the batch resampling methods based on LRP-heatmaps achieve a balancing effect, strongly improving performance w.r.t. the baseline on worse performing classes (e.g., 8–13, 45–53), but decreasing performance on better performing classes (e.g., 4–6, 8–13).

F1-Score Deviation from Baseline at Batch-Epoch 45									
Class (Age)	0–2	4–6	8–13	15–20	25–32	38–43	48–53	60+	Mean
Batch Resampling Method									
Data (%)	+4.5	+3.1	+8.0	+8.3	+0.4	+2.2	+20.4	+9.1	+7.0
Entropy (%)	+6.4	-10.2	-6.3	+14.1	-9.8	+1.1	+25.1	-3.8	+2.1
Sum of Positive Relevances (%)	+4.2	-5.3	-0.4	+14.2	-11.3	+1.9	+25.0	+10.7	+4.9
MSE-Distance (%)	+1.3	-22.1	-15.3	+12.2	-9.8	+1.6	+26.7	+0.7	-0.6

F1-score: A batch resampling favoring classes that are more difficult to understand for the network emphasizes their importance, and, subsequently, leads to a rise in the network’s performance on them. But in turn it also reduces the performance on classes that are more easily understood by the network. This indicates the class-wise performance balancing effect we aimed to achieve, as described in Section 1.1. However, more classes seem to decrease in performance than to increase for the LRP-heatmap-based metrics, leading to an overall worse F1-score than for the baseline models. Following this, it would thus be an evident topic of research for future work to develop a more regularized variant of LRP-based batch resampling that leads to a weaker, more controlled effect, resulting in a more optimal model.

This notion is further supported by Figure 6.3. Here, the class-wise F1-score over training time is shown for different batch resampling rules. Compared to the baseline models (*top left*), when resampling the data-batches according to the data distribution of the training set (*top right*), we find that the models converge much faster, because they reach higher class-wise performances earlier. E.g., at batch-epoch 45 (see Table 6.2) and barely change afterwards, with only a 1.2 % increase in class-wise F1-scores on average between batch-epochs 45 and 100. In contrast, when resampling according to the metrics based on LRP-heatmaps (*middle left, middle right, bottom*), the training does not seem to converge as fast. However, from a class-wise perspective, it seems more stable, since performance is gained on all classes at the same time: The mean and variance of the differences in performance between best and worst class over all batch-epochs is higher for the baseline and the batch resampling using the training data distribution than when employing the LRP-heatmap-based metrics (Table 6.3). E.g., the F1-score on age class 48–53 starts to increase far later than that on the other classes for the baseline and the resampling based on the training data distribution. Furthermore, in comparison, the class-wise F1-score stays closer together over the course of training for the resampling based on LRP-heatmap-metrics (e.g., the maximum difference in F1-score between classes

TABLE 6.3: Mean and standard deviation over all batch-epochs of the differences in performance between best and worst class respectively at each bath-epoch for the baseline and the four employed variations of batch resampling. A lower mean and standard deviation indicate a comparatively equal growth in performance of all classes, while a high mean or standard deviation shows large discrepancies in the performance gain of different classes over the course of training.

Mean and Standard Deviation of Class-wise Performance Difference		
Measure	Mean	Standard Deviation
Batch Resampling Method		
Baseline (%)	45.3	8.0
Data (%)	41.1	7.0
Entropy (%)	28.9	6.7
Sum of Positive Relevances (%)	32.9	8.2
MSE-Distance (%)	30.4	5.0

at any time during training is 40.2% when using the MSE-distance, but 59.8% for the baseline models). In fact, the LRP-heatmap-based class-wise weights even seem to react to an increasing divergence of class-wise performance, as the F1-score on class 0–2 (*blue*) decreases (e.g., when employing the entropy the F1-score of class 0–2 decreases from 31.1% at batch-epoch 20 to 18.0% at batch-epoch 26) after growing faster than for the other classes during the first batch-epochs.

However, for the sum of positive relevances in LRP-heatmaps, the class-wise F1-score starts diverging again around batch-epoch 45, coinciding with our assertion in Section 5.2 that the sum of positive relevances seems to be a comparatively unreliable measure due to its inherent noisiness. In contrast, the entropy of LRP-heatmaps and, especially, the MSE-distance of LRP-heatmaps seem to keep the class-wise F1-score relatively similar in a stable manner (Table 6.3). The decrease in overall F1-score in comparison to the baseline models results from only the classes on which the baseline models achieved the worst score (classes 15–20, 48–53) gaining any performance, while all other classes lose performance to varying degrees. Furthermore, the proposed batch resampling methods are still constrained by the availability of class-wise data: The fact that some classes simply offer more distinct datapoints than others cannot be completely mitigated by choosing more samples from minority classes, since they are prone to increased repetition from a certain point on, not offering the same amount of new information to the network as fresh samples from majority classes. Taking that into account, it is feasible to expect the observed trade-off in class-wise performances under the given circumstances.

Note that all metrics for Figure 6.3 were computed from samples of the training set. Figure 6.4 shows the average F1-score of the various batch resampling methods over batch-epochs, comparing the performance of LRP-heatmap-based resampling methods for heatmaps taken from test vs. training sets. It does not seem to matter for the resulting performance whether LRP-heatmaps are generated from training

FIGURE 6.4: Comparison of the average class-wise F1-score of the baseline models (red) and the models where batch resampling was applied during training, with the method based on the distribution of the training data (green) and LRP-heatmap-based methods using samples taken from the test set (orange) and training set (blue). Note that there is barely any difference (less than 2%) in performance in terms of whether the samples used for the LRP-heatmap computation are taken from the test set or the training set. The class-wise results can be found in Figure A.19

or from test samples. This allows for the application of the proposed LRP-heatmap-based batch resampling methods even if no test set is known, as only training samples are required, increasing their practicality.

We surmise that the LRP-heatmap-based methods for batch resampling manage to force the network to consider all classes equally, in relation to how easily their discriminative features are learned by the network. They do this equilization better than the batch resampling based on the training-set distribution, and thus demonstrate an assertion of the understanding the network has of the different classes at any point during training. They are further able to obtain this information from heatmaps generated from the training set or test set, both with similar results. While this method increases the performance on less understood classes, and thus achieves our aim of balancing the class-wise performances stated in Section 1.1, due to parallelly decreasing performance on better understood classes, it also leads to an overall reduction in the performance of the network, as the model can no longer rely on only concentrating on overpopulated classes in order to maximize its performance (i.e., it can no longer overfit as readily).

6.2 Scaling of Class-wise Losses

6.2.1 Method and Setup

Instead of making adjustments "before" the network, like in Chapter 6.1, we can also introduce changes "after" the network, similarly to the *Algorithm-focused* approaches described in Section 2.2. More precisely, we can tell the network to "pay more attention" to certain classes by scaling the class-wise losses during training utilizing class-wise weights similar to those in Section 6.1. However, in this experiment these are defined as $w_c \in]1, 2[$. The interval starts at 1 so that class-wise performance is

FIGURE 6.5: Average class-wise F1-score for the loss scaling based on different metrics. In contrast to the batch resampling method (Figure 6.1), the loss scaling does not seem to have much impact on the networks' performance.

not lost in comparison to the baseline, due to too slow learning. To avoid the drawbacks of too large class-wise losses, i.e., no proper convergence, the class-wise loss weights have an upper bound, here 2. These weights are obtained via the same metrics as in Section 6.1, however, an additional nonlinear step is appended to transform $w_c \in]0, 1[$ into the interval $]1, 2[$ while avoiding large weights, that is, applying the hyperbolic tangent (chosen heuristically) and adding 1. Otherwise, this experiment is set up identically to the experiment in Chapter 6.1.

6.2.2 Results and Discussion

Average performance of different methods to scale class-wise losses

In contrast to the batch resampling we applied in the previous Section (6.1), the scaling of class-wise losses barely seems to impact the training behavior of a network: As Figure 6.5 depicts, the performance achieved after 100 batch-epochs is very similar to the baseline models for all four loss scaling methods, with all final F1-scores lying in a 3%-interval, however, before that, the loss-scaled models seem to converge slightly faster than the baseline, as indicated by their higher area under the curves of the class-wise F1-scores (refer to Table 6.4). This effect can be found when utilizing the distribution of the training data, but is especially pronounced when the class-wise losses are scaled using the metrics based on LRP-heatmaps. More concisely, at batch-epoch 30 the models employing loss scaling based on the *Entropy of LRP-Heatmaps* reached an average F1-score of 33.2%, those employing the *Sum of Positive Relevances in LRP-Heatmaps* an average F1-score of 33.1%, and the models utilizing the *MSE-Distance of LRP-Heatmaps* an average F1-score of 35.4%. In contrast, the models that use the training-data distribution for scaling the class-wise losses only achieve an average F1-score of 30.9% at batch-epoch 30, while the baseline models only reach an F1-score of 29.4% on average at that batch-epoch. Towards the end of training, however, the average F1-score of the different methods converges to a similar value again.

FIGURE 6.6: Progression of the class-wise F1-score (smoothed) for the baseline models (*top left*) and for the models where class-wise loss scaling was applied during training. The original data can be found in Figure A.21. The results for using the distribution of the training data as a basis for this method are visualized in the (*top right*) and for the three LRP-heatmap-based metrics, i.e., entropy, sum of positive relevances, and MSE-distance in the (*middle left*), (*middle right*), and (*bottom*), respectively. The black lines indicate the lowest and highest class-wise performances at the last batch-epoch for each method. Note that all metrics for these results were computed from training samples. In contrast to the batch resampling method, barely any improvement towards a more balanced performance is discernible.

TABLE 6.4: Area under the curve of class-wise F1-scores (see Figure A.20) for the loss scaling methods, with a larger area indicating a faster convergence. The area under the curve is largest for the models employing loss scaling, especially when using LRP-heatmap-based metrics (entropy, sum of positive relevances, MSE-distance) for this purpose.

Area under the Curve								
Class (Age)	0–2	4–6	8–13	15–20	25–32	38–43	48–53	60+
Loss Scaling Method								
Baseline	80.18	87.19	79.13	70.69	37.48	72.57	40.10	79.20
Data	83.54	87.47	81.18	88.20	38.24	77.69	46.35	73.19
Entropy	85.46	89.02	80.49	88.68	37.82	80.16	51.92	82.23
Sum of Positive Relevances	86.39	87.94	82.71	87.19	41.07	82.80	57.62	89.54
MSE-Distance	86.01	91.82	84.63	66.23	41.82	86.44	49.17	84.92

Class-wise effects of different methods to scale class-wise losses

The class-wise effect (see Figures 6.6 and A.20) of scaling the class-wise losses is also not nearly as strong as for the batch resampling. While, in the latter case, we find a noticeable performance increase for the classes on which the baseline models achieve a lower F1-score and a performance decrease for the classes on which the baseline models attain a higher F1-score, the class-wise performances barely diverge from the baseline when scaling the losses. However, similarly to the effect we noted for the average F1-score in Figure 6.5, for all classes, except the ages 48–53, the models employing loss scaling based on LRP-heatmap-metrics converge equally fast or even faster than the baseline and the models using the training-data distribution (see Figures 6.5 and A.20). I.e., at batch-epoch 45, the loss scaling based on the sum of positive relevances of LRP-heatmaps reached an average F1-score of 46.0%, while models using the data-distribution and the baseline models only reached 44.0% and 39.2%, respectively. However, as final average F1-scores, those three methods arrived at 46.2%, 48.3% and 48.6%, respectively, showing the faster convergence of the LRP-heatmap-based variants.

While, as stated above, the convergence speed of the models seems to be increased when applying the class-wise loss scaling method using metrics based on LRP-heatmaps, Figure 6.6 shows that the class-wise F1-score is not behaving more similarly between classes than for the baseline, thus not indicating the more balanced performance we aimed to achieve in Section 1.1, especially for class 48–53, where no difference between baseline models and models employing loss scaling in terms of when the F1-score begins to increase is discernible. However, that goal was met by the batch resampling method in Section 6.1 employing the same LRP-heatmap-based metrics that were utilized for scaling the class-wise losses. We can thus infer that the root of this problem lies with the loss scaling method, and not with the LRP-heatmap-based metrics. The batch resampling method may be more impactful than the loss scaling method, since it makes adaptations *before* the networks'

learning algorithm is applied. Resampling the data-batch makes more samples available for classes that are more difficult to learn, affecting the average error signal per class. The batch resampling may thereby provide more information to the training process than the loss scaling, e.g., by requiring more changes in weights with more detailed gradients. Thus, the scaling of class-wise losses may only affect the networks' behavior in a localized manner, e.g., by slightly changing the class-wise convergence speed, but not in a more global manner, e.g., by augmenting the shape of the class-wise performance curves or changing when the performance on single classes increases or decreases.

For this reason, we conclude that the class-wise loss scaling method is not able to use the expressive power of LRP-heatmaps to its full extent, as it is applied at a too late stage during the learning step. In contrast, the data-batch resampling method is able to force a more balanced class-wise performance.

Key Insights

- LRP-heatmaps and secondary metrics derived from them were employed successfully to balance the class-wise performance of a NN by resampling the data-batches on-line during training.
- This balancing method was employed with no discernible difference when using LRP-heatmaps derived from samples of the test set compared to LRP-heatmaps from the training set, allowing it to be applied even without having access to test data.
- The effect of utilizing the LRP-heatmaps for this purpose is, however, dependent on the stage of the learning algorithm that is augmented.

Chapter 7

Conclusions and Outlook

Over the course of this thesis, we explored the expressive power of Layer-wise Relevance Propagation (LRP) as a means for measuring the understanding a neural network (NN) has of a given task through various experiments. For this purpose, we firstly derived secondary metrics from the LRP-heatmaps in order to make them comparable to traditional evaluation metrics, i.e., the accuracy and F1-score on the test set. Here, we found that these secondary metrics, and, by extension, the heatmaps generated by LRP, showed a very strong correlation to the traditional evaluation metrics over a NN's training time, thus, by extension, indicating that they can be applied to estimate a model's performance and convergence. In fact, we obtained these results for heatmaps that were computed w.r.t. the *predicted* class labels, thus potentially allowing for the omission of true label information and imposing less restrictions in terms of applicability than the employed traditional evaluation metrics that require labeled test data. Furthermore, the secondary metrics based on LRP-heatmaps were able to detect changes in the networks' learning progress before the traditional evaluation metrics. In these respects, we can thus conclude that the LRP-heatmaps pose a more powerful method for measuring a NN's understanding than the test accuracy or the F1-score. However, in turn, the computation of LRP-heatmaps is not model-agnostic like the traditional evaluation metrics we employed.

Secondly, we found the LRP-heatmap-based metrics capable of establishing a clear class-wise order, distinguishing classes that the network is able to predict correctly with a high certainty from classes which the network is mostly predicting incorrectly. This order correlates to the one suggested by the class-wise traditional evaluation metrics, however, without being influenced in favor of majority classes in an imbalanced data setting, as is the case for the class-wise test accuracy and the F1-score.

Building on these properties, we applied the LRP heatmaps and the secondary metrics based on them practically. Here, we found that when adapting a NN's training process in a class-wise manner based on LRP-heatmaps, a more balanced performance can be achieved on imbalanced data. This means that, when using the LRP-heatmap-based metrics to redistribute the data-batch for each batch-epoch, we observed a clear increase in performance on the classes with a previously small F1-score and a decrease for the classes with a previously large F1-score. Furthermore, learning progression on all classes started immediately in a relatively equal manner, whereas before the performance on some classes did not increase until later batch-epochs. Here, the results were not affected by whether the samples for computing LRP-heatmaps were chosen from the test set or the training set, making this method

applicable even without having access to a test set. When comparing different methods of utilizing the LRP-heatmaps for the purpose of equalizing the networks' class-wise performance, we found that techniques which perform augmentations at an earlier stage in the forward-backward-propagation learning step have a larger impact in that respect. E.g., the *Batch Resampling* method strongly influences the shape and course of the class-wise performances, affecting the networks' training process in an extremely detailed manner. In comparison, the *Scaling of Class-wise Losses* seems to provide less information to the models' training process, since it does not offer more samples of classes that are difficult to learn, and thereby only influences the networks' convergence speed, but does not make further in-depth changes to the training behavior.

We conclude that the heatmaps generated by LRP are extremely promising for evaluating a NN's understanding of the data and indicative of its generalization performance, even without requiring labeled test data. Furthermore, in an imbalanced data setting, while the effect of the inherent imbalance of the data cannot be completely negated, using the right method LRP-heatmaps can be applied to mitigate it and reach a more equalized classification performance, making them very promising for real-world applications and automatically collected datasets where inherent imbalances in the training data cannot always be avoided.

In this thesis we largely restricted the task and model, and while we touched upon the generalizability of our results by utilizing different initialization weights and augmenting the Adience dataset label assignment, further research into if and how the above results hold on a broader spectrum of settings would be advantageous in the future. Furthermore, as there is no need for labeled test data to compute the proposed LRP-heatmap-based metrics, further exploration into how they can be employed to estimate performance on unlabeled real-world data or applied to model and dataset selection seems promising.

Appendix

Layer (type)	Output Shape	Param #
input_1 (InputLayer)	(None, 224, 224, 3)	0
block1_conv1 (Conv2D)	(None, 224, 224, 64)	1792
block1_conv2 (Conv2D)	(None, 224, 224, 64)	36928
block1_pool (MaxPooling2D)	(None, 112, 112, 64)	0
block2_conv1 (Conv2D)	(None, 112, 112, 128)	73856
block2_conv2 (Conv2D)	(None, 112, 112, 128)	147584
block2_pool (MaxPooling2D)	(None, 56, 56, 128)	0
block3_conv1 (Conv2D)	(None, 56, 56, 256)	295168
block3_conv2 (Conv2D)	(None, 56, 56, 256)	590080
block3_conv3 (Conv2D)	(None, 56, 56, 256)	590080
block3_pool (MaxPooling2D)	(None, 28, 28, 256)	0
block4_conv1 (Conv2D)	(None, 28, 28, 512)	1180160
block4_conv2 (Conv2D)	(None, 28, 28, 512)	2359808
block4_conv3 (Conv2D)	(None, 28, 28, 512)	2359808
block4_pool (MaxPooling2D)	(None, 14, 14, 512)	0
block5_conv1 (Conv2D)	(None, 14, 14, 512)	2359808
block5_conv2 (Conv2D)	(None, 14, 14, 512)	2359808
block5_conv3 (Conv2D)	(None, 14, 14, 512)	2359808
block5_pool (MaxPooling2D)	(None, 7, 7, 512)	0
flatten_1 (Flatten)	(None, 25088)	0
dense_1 (Dense)	(None, 4096)	102764544
dropout_1 (Dropout)	(None, 4096)	0
dense_2 (Dense)	(None, 4096)	16781312
dropout_2 (Dropout)	(None, 4096)	0
dense_3 (Dense)	(None, 8)	32776
Total params: 134,293,320		
Trainable params: 134,293,320		
Non-trainable params: 0		

TABLE A.1: (to Section 4.1): Visualization of the VGG-16 network architecture (Simonyan and Zisserman, 2014) employed for age classification on the Adience dataset. This network consists of 16 layers, beginning with groups of convolutional layers with small kernel sizes (2 to 3) alternating with pooling operations, yielding a very deep model. Then follow two large dense layers, each consisting of 4096 hidden units. For regularization purposes, these dense layers alternate with two dropout layers with a dropout probability of 50% each.

FIGURE A.1 (to Section 5.1): Comparison of different computation variants for the class-wise Shannon-Entropy of LRP-heatmaps over batch-epochs. Depicted are the entropy computed from LRP-heatmaps w.r.t. the predicted class (left) and true class (right). For the (top) two subfigures, the binning is performed over the value range of each respective heatmap, after normalizing it w.r.t. its largest absolute relevance (Local Binning, with the value range depending on each respective heatmap). In contrast, for the (bottom) results, the bins are spanning the global value range of all LRP-heatmaps during a network’s training process (Global Binning, with the value range $[\min(R^*), \max(R^*)]$ where R^* denotes the set of all LRP-heatmaps computed during training). Here, the locally binned variants show the highest discriminativity between classes and the ordering that best aligns with that suggested by the F1-scores, albeit reversed (compare with Figure 5.5 for reference). The global binning is about 10 times smaller in magnitude and leads to the class-wise ordering not corresponding as closely to that suggested by the F1-scores. For the local binning, only slight differences exist between results for heatmaps w.r.t. the predicted and true classes. However, for the global binning, there is a large discrepancy. While the entropy of LRP-heatmaps w.r.t. the predicted class steadily increases and is relatively separable class-wise — although not as persistently as for the local binning —, the entropy of LRP-heatmaps w.r.t. the true class is not as consistent and has an enormous discrepancy in magnitude for better (e.g., age classes 0–2, 4–6) and worse performing classes (e.g., age classes 38–43, 48–53).

FIGURE A.2 (to Section 5.1): Same heatmaps as in Figure 5.1, but normalized w.r.t. the highest absolute relevance over *all* 100 batch-epochs.

FIGURE A.3 (to Section 5.2): Same heatmaps as in Figure 5.3, but normalized w.r.t. the highest absolute relevance over the 16 shown batch-epochs.

FIGURE A.4 (to Section 5.2): (Figure continued on next page)

FIGURE A.4 (to Section 5.2): Correlation between (traditional) evaluation metrics and LRP-heatmap-based metrics for different weight initializations over training time. Initializations are increasing in terms of transferred previous knowledge from (top) to (bottom): Random-, ImageNet, IMDB-WIKI-, and Adience-initialization. The respective correlation coefficient is denoted as ρ in each subfigure. The LRP-heatmap-based metrics show a strongly positive correlation to the traditional evaluation metrics, especially to the F1-score for the Adience-initialized models. These results also hold for the ImageNet and IMDB-WIKI-initialization, however, for the randomly initialized models this correlation is negative.

FIGURE A.5 (to Section 5.2): (Figure continued on next page)

FIGURE A.5 (to Section 5.2): (Figure continued on next page)

FIGURE A.5 (to Section 5.2): Class-wise correlation between (traditional) evaluation metrics and LRP-heatmap-based metrics for the age classes not depicted in Figure 5.4 over training time (Adience-initialization). The respective correlation coefficient is denoted as ρ in each subfigure. The general observations made in Figure 5.2 also seem to hold for the single classes, especially the correlation of the metrics based on LRP-heatmaps to the F1-score.

FIGURE A.6 (to Section 5.2): Comparison of the F1-score (blue) and MSE-distance (orange) of LRP-heatmaps. The MSE-distance is able to pick up subtle changes in the heatmaps before the traditional evaluation metrics.

FIGURE A.7 (to Section 5.2): Class-wise **F1-Score** for different weight initializations. The initializations used are as follows, sorted in terms of their offered previous knowledge about the task: Random- (top left), ImageNet- (top right), IMDB-WIKI- (bottom left), and Adience-initialization (bottom right). The models with a higher amount of previous knowledge achieve higher F1-score, on average.

FIGURE A.8 (to Section 5.2): Class-wise **Entropy of LRP-Heatmaps** for different weight initializations. The initializations used are as follows, sorted in terms of their offered previous knowledge about the task: Random- (*top left*), ImageNet- (*top right*), IMDB-WIKI- (*bottom left*), and Adience-initialization (*bottom right*). In terms of class-wise ordering, the results found for the Adience-initialization seem to also hold for the other weight initializations, except for the Random-initialization. Here, the class-wise ordering is reversed in the beginning, but seems to change later in training, aligning with the ordering of the other weight initializations.

FIGURE A.9 (to Section 5.2): Class-wise **Sum of Positive Relevance** in LRP-Heatmaps for different weight initializations. The initializations used are as follows, sorted in terms of their offered previous knowledge about the task: Random- (top left), ImageNet- (top right), IMDB-WIKI- (bottom left), and Adience-initialization (bottom right). In terms of class-wise ordering, the results found for the Adience-initialization seem to also hold for the other weight initializations, except for the Random-initialization. Here, the class-wise ordering is reversed in the beginning, but seems to change later in training, aligning with the ordering of the other weight initializations.

FIGURE A.10 (to Section 5.2): Class-wise MSE-distance of LRP-Heatmaps for different weight initializations. The initializations used are as follows, sorted in terms of their offered previous knowledge about the task: Random- (*top left*), ImageNet- (*top right*), IMDB-WIKI- (*bottom left*), and Adience-initialization (*bottom right*). Note that with increasing previous knowledge, the MSE-distance gets *absolutely* smaller on average, but *relatively* decreases less monotonously. Instead, it grows larger, especially during the first batch epochs. In terms of class-wise ordering, the results found for the Adience-initialization seem to also hold for the other weight initializations, except for the Random-initialization. Here, the class-wise ordering is reversed in the beginning, but seems to change later in training, aligning with the ordering of the other weight initializations.

FIGURE A.11 (to Section 5.2): Class-wise **F1-Score** for different tasks, i.e., gender classification (*top left*) and age classification with 2, 3, 4, 5, or 8 distinct labels.

FIGURE A.12 (to Section 5.2): Class-wise **Entropy of LRP-Heatmaps** for different tasks, i.e., gender classification (*top left*) and age classification with 2, 3, 4, 5, or 8 distinct labels. The results obtained for 8 age labels (*bottom right*) seem to hold for all task variations except the binary classification, where the class-wise ordering is reversed in comparison, probably due to binary classification being a special case where the performance on both classes is extremely similar and a decision against one class is automatically a decision for the other class.

FIGURE A.13 (to Section 5.2): Class-wise **Sum of Positive Relevances** in LRP-Heatmaps for different tasks, i.e., gender classification (*top left*) and age classification with 2, 3, 4, 5, or 8 distinct labels. Over various tasks, the behavior of this measure seems to be quite noisy, especially compared to the other LRP-heatmap-based metrics.

FIGURE A.14 (to Section 5.2): Class-wise **MSE-distance of LRP-Heatmaps** for different tasks, i.e., gender classification (*top left*) and age classification with 2, 3, 4, 5, or 8 distinct labels. Note that the more complex the task becomes, the less the MSE-distance monotonously decreases. Instead, it grows larger in the beginning before descending, and this behavior holds for more batch-epochs if the task is more complex.

FIGURE A.15 (to Section 5.2): Binary classification heatmaps for the gender classification and 2-label-age-classification task. The heatmaps are computed w.r.t. the *predicted* class and normalized into the interval $[-1, 1]$, where those of the classes "male" and "younger" are surer, less diverging, and contain more positive relevances than their respective counterparts. The heatmaps of especially the binary age classification model seem to be strongly influenced by the model's biases in the last layer (positive for "older" and negative for "younger"). When employing LRP, relevance is "lost" to the biases (Lapuschkin, 2019) and this effect seems to lead to the mainly negative relevances for the heatmaps for the "older" class. For comparison, Figure A.16 shows the results for the binary age classification when keeping the last-layer bias at zero.

FIGURE A.16 (to Section 5.2): Binary classification heatmaps for the 2-age-classification task when keeping the last-layer bias at zero. The heatmaps are computed w.r.t. the *predicted* class and normalized into the interval $[-1, 1]$. In contrast to Figure A.15, the heatmaps contain far more positive relevances, thus behaving as expected for heatmaps w.r.t. the *predicted* class and demonstrating the effect of biases in the last layer on those heatmaps.

FIGURE A.17 (to Section 6.1): Performance comparison of the various metrics that are utilized for resampling the data-batches during training. The results for the three metrics based on LRP-heatmaps, i.e., entropy, sum of positive relevances, and MSE-distance, are visualized by the (blue), (orange), and (green) lines, respectively. The performance of the batch resampling using the distribution of the training data is shown in red, while the baseline, i.e., not adapting the training process in any way, is depicted in purple. This comparison is visualized for each of the eight age classes of the Adience benchmark dataset, except for ages 8–13 and 48–53, which were already depicted in Figure 6.2. The average class-wise F1-score is employed as a measure of performance. Note that, while the LRP-heatmap-based methods, especially when using the MSE-distance, obtain a lower F1-score on better performing classes, e.g., ages 4–6, they in turn achieve a far higher F1-score than the baseline models or the models employing training-distribution-based batch resampling on worse performing classes, e.g., ages 15–20.

FIGURE A.18 (to Section 6.1): Progression of the class-wise F1-score (original data) for the baseline models (top left), and for the models where batch resampling was applied during training. The results for using the distribution of the training data as a basis for this method are visualized in the (top right) and for the three LRP-heatmap-based metrics, i.e., entropy, sum of positive relevances, and MSE-distance in the (middle left), (middle right), and (bottom), respectively. For each of these variations, the variance of average class-wise F1-scores at batch-epoch 100 is denoted as σ^2 and the maximum difference between highest and lowest class-wise performance during training is visualized as a black arrow. Note that all metrics for these results were computed from training samples. In comparison to the baseline models, the training-distribution-based batch resampling achieved the same performance slightly faster. The LRP-heatmap-based methods, however, managed to force the network towards a far more balanced class-wise performance (see the lower variance σ^2 at batch-epoch 100 for the LRP-heatmap-based metrics), considering all classes in a comparatively equal manner from the start, and achieving far lower differences in class-wise performance than the baseline or data-distribution-based batch resampling (black arrows).

FIGURE A.19 (to Section 6.1): (Figure continued on next page)

FIGURE A.19 (to Section 6.1): (Class-wise) comparison of the average class-wise F1-score of the baseline models (*red*) and the models where batch resampling was applied during training, with the method based on the distribution of the training data (*green*) and LRP-heatmap-based methods using samples taken from the test set (*orange*) and training set (*blue*).

FIGURE A.20 (to Section 6.2): (Figure continued on next page)

FIGURE A.20 (to Section 6.2): Performance comparison of the various metrics that are utilized for scaling the class-wise losses during training. The results for the three metrics based on LRP-heatmaps, i.e., entropy, sum of positive relevances, and MSE-distance is visualized by the (*blue*), (*orange*), and (*green*) lines, respectively. The performance of the loss-scaling using the distribution of the training data is shown in (*red*), while the baseline, i.e., not adapting the training process in any way, is depicted in (*purple*). This comparison is visualized for each of the eight age classes of the Adience benchmark dataset. The average class-wise F1-score is employed as a measure of performance. In contrast to the batch resampling method (see Figures 6.2 and A.17), the loss scaling method used does not have a lot of impact on the networks' performance.

FIGURE A.21 (to Section 6.2): Progression of the class-wise F1-score (original data) for the baseline models (top left) and for the models where class-wise loss scaling was applied during training. The results for using the distribution of the training data as a basis for this method are visualized in the (top right) and for the three LRP-heatmap-based metrics, i.e., entropy, sum of positive relevances, and MSE-distance in the (middle left), (middle right), and (bottom), respectively. Note that all metrics for these results were computed from training samples. In contrast to the batch resampling method, barely any improvement towards a more balanced performance is discernible.

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